

TELLING, TRANSLATING, TILTING

The Surprising Reception History of 1 Cor. 16:2

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COVER IMAGE

Image with part of 1 Cor. 16 in the *Codex Mentelin Bibel*, MS (1466). Image in Public Domain, digitized by Universitätsbibliothek Freiburg. (Online-Ausg.: Freiburg i. Br.: Univ.-Bibl., 2014 Online-Ressource (Freiburger historische Bestände - digital. Freiburger Handschriften ; Hs. 22a) <https://dl.ub.uni-freiburg.de/diglit/hs22a/0687>).

REFERENCES

Preferably make references to the original Dutch thesis:

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ABOUT THIS ENGLISH TRANSLATION

This is an English translation of Tony Jurg's thesis, which was written in partial fulfilment of the requirements for obtaining a Bachelor's degree in theology at Tilburg School of Catholic Theology (TST). The thesis was supervised by Prof. Paul van Geest, with Prof. Caroline vander Stichele serving as the second assessor. The original Dutch title of the thesis was "Vertellen, Vertalen en Vertillen: De Receptiegeschiedenis van 1 Kor. 16,2."¹ The defense took place on February 3rd, 2022, in Utrecht, The Netherlands. This translation is not a substitute for the original thesis but aims to make the information more accessible to an English-speaking audience. It is preferred to refer to the original Dutch thesis, available at Tilburg University,² when referencing this research in any publication.

This English translation aims to make the original accessible to a wider audience while still presenting the original thesis in a clear and accurate manner. It closely follows the content of the Dutch original, with only limited changes indicated by footnotes indicating such additions. A few typing errors have been corrected, but no arguments have been added, changed, or removed. Due to a strict word count limitation, information in the original thesis was presented in a very condensed manner. To improve readability, this translation includes a limited amount of clarification and expansion of terms where regarded helpful.

One significant difference from the original is the handling of quotes in Greek, Latin, German, or Dutch. In the original thesis, these quotes were presented inline without translation to save on wordlength. In this translation, most of these foreign language quotes have been moved to footnotes and replaced in the running text with an English translation. Some smaller foreign language quotations were left in the main text, but for most an English translation has been added in the footnotes. Additionally, some adaptations have been made to accommodate the English language, such as changes in transliteration methodology and references to sources like the Catechism of the Catholic Church.

Regarding typography, various formatting changes have been made. One notable change is the conversion of references to biblical sources from the Tilburg University style to the guidelines of the Society of Biblical Literature (SBL) which also impacted the fonts used for Greek and Hebrew text. Additionally, minor formatting adaptations have been applied, particularly to indented text blocks, which now use a smaller font size.

¹ To convey its content in a captivating manner, the Dutch title relies on alliteration, the repetition of initial consonant sounds in three syllables. This rhythmic effect is partially maintained in the English title by using three words that start with the same letter.

² <http://arno.uvt.nl/show.cgi?fid=158320>.

INTRODUCTION

Motive

This research was prompted by the observation that Luther, by means of a literal *verdeutschung* (German rendering), translated 1 Cor. 16:2^a in his September testament (1522) as: “*auff iah der Sabbater eynen lege bey sich selbs eyn yglicher unter euch.*”³ When acquainted with the biblical spring festivals, this formulation evokes associations with the Omer Period. The use of the underlying Greek idiom *μίαν σαββάτων*,⁴ which is also found in the ‘resurrection verses’ describing events at the beginning of the Omer Period, further reinforces this association.

However, modern translations render this idiom entirely differently with variations on ‘every first day of the week.’ This raises questions about historical text reception and the background of the altered translation. Was Paul in fact referring to the Omer Period or was no alternative idiom available to prevent later ambiguity?

An inquiry into the *status quaestionis* did not yield scientific articles that provide answers to any of these questions.⁵ No diachronic inquiry (from *δια* ‘through’ and *χρόνος* ‘time’) into the translation of 1 Cor. 16:2 seemed to be available. Equally, research based primarily on intertextuality with the LXX⁶ on how *κατὰ μίαν σαββάτων* was understood at the time of Paul and his audience, seems to be missing.

Research questions

The central research question of this thesis is:

What is the cause of the translation change of *κατὰ μίαν σαββάτων*?

This question suggests that there was a significant translation change and that it is possible to determine the time and place of this change with reasonable certainty. In order to provide a valid response to the central research question, it is necessary to conduct a preliminary investigation into these implicit assumptions. For this purpose, the following sub-questions have been formulated:

1. How was 1 Cor. 16:2 translated in different ancient bibles?
2. What is the historical context of the translation change?
3. Does the ‘old way of translation’ deliver a meaningful exegesis?

The necessity of the first sub-question lies in determining the ‘when’ and ‘where’ of the translation change, while the second addresses the ‘why.’ The third sub-question is necessary to determine whether this was a substantial or a trivial translation change. An example of a technical need for a trivial change (in this case, a change from ‘first’ to ‘seventh’ day of the week) arose in 1972 (in the

³ Internet Archive, “Das Neue Testament Deutsch, 1522”, visited 13 October 2021, <https://archive.org/details/DasNeueTestamentDeutsch1522/page/n286/mode/1up>

⁴ According to Luther's source text (*Textus Receptus*).

⁵ However, there are countless publications, commentaries and lexicons which cite the *μίαν σαββάτων* in the resurrection verses (because of Easter Sunday) as supporting argument for the translation ‘first day of the week’ in 1 Cor. 16:2.

⁶ Septuagint: Greek-language Tanakh.

Netherlands) when the 'first day of the week' officially shifted from Sunday to Monday.⁷

Presuppositions

Every researcher uses presuppositions, often without explicit mentioning them. The preliminary starting point in this thesis is that Paul considered the Tanakh authoritative and remained part of the extremely diverse Judaism of his time. This is based, among other things, on the way the book of Acts, written many years after the letter to the Corinthians, portrays Paul as a law-abiding Jew.⁸

Key terms and spellings

A cursory glance at church history shows that there has been considerable debate about the content, form, and dating of the Passion period, resulting in significant conceptual confusion. To facilitate a clear discussion, this thesis uses unambiguous key terms, recognizable by their capitalization.⁹ Each key term is further categorized as belonging to either the biblical or ecclesiastical domain:¹⁰

Biblical key terms: Sabbath, Passover, Unleavened Bread, Yom Rishon, Wave Sheaf Offering,¹¹ Omer Period, and Feast of Weeks.

Ecclesiastical key terms: Saturday, Good Friday, Easter, Easter Sunday, Sunday, and Pentecost.

For Hebrew-language key terms, the usual spelling has been applied to generally known concepts (such as Sabbath), while in other cases, the transliteration of the Society of Biblical Literature (SBL) has been followed.¹² Wherever Biblical and ecclesiastical key terms mostly overlap, this is indicated with the symbol '≈' ('is approximately equal to'). For example: Wave Sheaf Offering (≈ Easter Sunday).¹³

Because content and structure of the biblical festivals cannot be assumed to be generally known, this is clarified in Appendix 3, where a diagram illustrates the interrelationship between the biblical and ecclesiastical key terms listed above.

This thesis is largely based on primary source documents, which have been reproduced in their original spelling whenever possible. Square brackets indicate unintelligible parts and/or missing portions.

⁷ NEN 2772:1972. (NEN: Dutch standardization institute).

⁸ Acts 24:14-16, 25:8, 26:22, and 28:17.

⁹ Analogous to capitalization of explicitly defined legal terms and concepts.

¹⁰ Without implying *a priori* contradictions.

¹¹ More commonly known as 'Feast of Firstfruits'. This designation is not used here due to its ambiguity, as Ex. 23:16 also associates the Feast of Weeks with firstfruits.

¹² Based upon The SBL Handbook of Style (second edition).

¹³ Sunsets define the boundaries of Biblical days (cf. Lev. 23:32).

PRELUDE

Introduction

Translations never originate in isolation from their historical context, as translators are influenced by previous commentators and translations. To provide some helpful background information, this prelude sketches some contours on the *verstehen*¹⁴ of *μίαν σαββάτων* by important early church commentators. It will also examine whether their argumentation was theological or grammatical in nature. This section will close with a reflection on allusions to the 'day of the Lord' during the first centuries.

Early commentators

Justin Martyr (c. 100-165)

Justin Martyr is the first to unequivocally mention a special position of Sunday, which he calls *ἡλίου λεγομένη ἡμέρα*. His argumentation for this was by no means grammatical, but exemplary of a *sensus spiritualis*:

(...) *But the day of the sun* (Τὴν δὲ τοῦ ἡλίου ἡμέραν) we all hold our common assembly, because *it is the first day* (πρώτη ἐστὶν ἡμέρα) on which God, having wrought a change in the darkness and matter, made the world; and Jesus Christ our Savior on the same day rose from the dead. For He was crucified on *the day before that of Saturn* (πρὸ τῆς Κρονικῆς); and on *the day after Saturn* (τῇ μετὰ τὴν Κρονικὴν), which *is the day of the Sun* (ἐστὶν ἡλίου ἡμέρα), having appeared to His apostles and disciples, (...).¹⁵

Chrysostom (c. 345-407)

Chrysostom quotes in his homily *περὶ ἐλεημοσύνης* Paul's instruction on ingathering: *Μίαν σαββάτων τὴν κυριακὴν ἐκάλεσε*.¹⁶ The ingathering should take place at the 'appointed time' (*καιροῦ*) and not on *δευτέρα* or *τριτητῶν σαββάτων* or any other day.¹⁷ It appears from the whole of the homily that Chrysostom probably understood *μίαν σαββάτων* as 'Sunday'. For Chrysostom, too, the argument seems to be mainly theological in nature.

¹⁴ Concept introduced by Max Weber (1864-1920) and applied to hermeneutics by Schleiermacher (1768-1834). It indicates 'understanding, accepting'.

¹⁵ The Greek text: "Τὴν δὲ τοῦ ἡλίου ἡμέραν κοινῇ πάντες τὴν συνέλευσιν ποιούμεθα, ἐπειδὴ πρώτη ἐστὶν ἡμέρα, ἐν ἧ ὁ θεὸς, τὸ σκότος καὶ τὴν ὕλην τρέψας, κόσμον ἐποίησε, καὶ Ἰησοῦς Χριστὸς ὁ ἡμέτερος Σωτὴρ τῇ αὐτῇ ἡμέρᾳ ἐκ νεκρῶν ἀνέστη. Τῇ γὰρ πρὸ τῆς Κρονικῆς ἐσταύρωσαν αὐτόν, καὶ τῇ μετὰ τὴν Κρονικὴν, ἣτις ἐστὶν ἡλίου ἡμέρα, φανεῖς τοῖς ἀποστόλοις αὐτοῦ" in Justin Martyr, "Apologia I,67" in *PG, tomus VI, tomus unicus*, ed. J.-P. Migne (Parisina: J.-P. Migne, 1857), col. 429&432. The provided English text is based upon the following translation: Justin Martyr, "The First Apology of Justin," in *The Apostolic Fathers with Justin Martyr and Irenaeus*, ed. Alexander Roberts, James Donaldson, and A. Cleveland Coxe, vol. 1, The Ante-Nicene Fathers (Buffalo, NY: Christian Literature Company, 1885), 186.

¹⁶ Chrysostom, "De Eleemosyna γ" in *PG, tomus LI, tomus tertii*, ed. J.-P. Migne (Parisina: J.-P. Migne, 1859), col. 264gr.

¹⁷ Ibid.

Augustine of Hippo (354-430)

Augustine's argument for (the special position of the) Sunday is also primarily theological. Where the Greek text has *μίαν σαββάτων*, Augustine states it is allowed to read *una* as *prima*. In his justification, Augustine does not present any grammatical arguments but instead refers to the resurrection of Christ:

Nam dies resurrectionis Domini, prima sabbati a Matthæo, acæteris autem tribus una sabbati dicitur.¹⁸

Theophylactus of Nicomedia (c. 1055-1107)

Theophylactus was a Byzantine exegete known as *expositor graecus* and author of a series of commentaries on Paul's letters. These commentaries were frequently published in print at the end of the Middle Ages and were therefore very influential. Theophylactus's argument is like that of Augustine but included a more grammatical undertone. The Greek and Latin text of his commentary on 1 Cor. 16:2 as in *Patrologiæ græce* contains:

Μίαν Σαββάτων τὴν Κυριακὴν καλεῖ, ἀντὶ τοῦ, τὴν πρώτην τῶν τοῦ Σαββάτου ἡμέρας ἢ τῆς ἐβδομάδος ἡμερῶν./ Unam Sabbatorum Dominicam vocat, hoc est primam Sabbati vel hebdomadis dierum.¹⁹

Migne's Latin translation understands *sabbati* as 'week' but does not equate 'day of the Lord' with 'the first day of the week' (= Sunday) as is the case in the Latin translation by Christophoro Porsena from 1529:

Per vna[m] sabbati, d[om]inicum die[m] intelligit, hoc est, prima[m] sabbati, vel primu[m] hebdomadæ die[m].²⁰

These translation variations thus reveal the fluid conceptual content of the word 'Sabbath' at that time.

Nicholas de Lyra (c. 1270-1349)

As the first printed Biblical exegesis, de Lyra's 50-volume 'Postillae perpetuæ',²¹ had great influence after the Middle Ages. To compose his commentaries, de Lyra utilized many sources including the ones by his rabbinical counterpart Rashi. De Lyra emphasized the *sensus literalis* above an allegorical or mystical reading. In line with this, de Lyra was probably the first to understand *μίαν σαββάτων* as 'first day of the week' not solely based on theological grounds, but also explicitly defended this understanding with grammatical arguments:

Per vnam fab. Idest, prima die hebdomadæ, que vocatur sabbatum in pluribus locis scripturæ vnde Luca. 18.b. Ieiuno bis in sabbato i[dest]. in hebdomada. Similiter vna accipitur pro prima Gen.1.a. Factu[m] est mane [?] vespere die vnus. Ita enim

¹⁸ Augustine, "Epistola XXXVI,XI,28" in *PL, tomus XXXIII, tomus secundus*, ed. J.-P. Migne (Parisina: J.-P. Migne, 1865), col. 149.

¹⁹ Theophylactus, "Exposition in Epist. 1 Ad Cor. Cap. XVI". *PG, tomus CXXIV, tomus secundus*, ed. J.-P. Migne (Parisina: J.-P. Migne, 1864), col. 785-786.

²⁰ Theophylactus, *Theophylacti archiepiscopi Bulgariae in omnes divi Pauli epistolas enarrationes ...*, trans. Christophoro Porsena (Coloniæ: Petri Quentel, 1527), I Epist. ad Corinth. enarratio, fol. LII.

²¹ Rome, 1471-1472.

ōcfeuerāt fideles cōunenire ad ecclesia dominica die, qua est hebdomadis prima dies, propter q[?] dicte collecta.²²

The day of the Lord

The concept 'day of the Lord' requires specific attention. This clearly referred to the weekly Sunday. This is evident from his description of a 14-day sea voyage in which a 'day of the Lord' occurs twice:

ubi et ipse Apostolus navigabat, quatuordecim diebus, ac per hoc duobus dominicis je junatum (Act.xxvii, 33).²³

Concerning the understanding of κυριακῆ ἡμέρα as the (weekly) Sunday, C.W. Dugmore states: "It is sometimes worth reconsidering what most people regard as a *chose jugée*, even if no startling conclusions can be definitely proved."²⁴ He remarks, "is it not remarkable how little evidence there is in the New Testament and in the literature of the Sub-Apostolic age that Sunday was the most important day in the Christian Week".²⁵ Early allusions to the 'day of the Lord,' such as in *Didache* 14:1, are, according to Dugmore, more appropriately applicable to Easter Sunday than to the weekly Sunday.²⁶ Kenneth. A. Strand²⁷ adds to this observation with the following reference to Irenæus:

This [custom], of not bending the knee upon Sunday,²⁸ is a symbol of the resurrection [...] Irenæus, the martyr and bishop of Lyons, declares in his treatise On Easter,²⁹ in which he makes mention of Pentecost also; upon which [feast] we do not bend the knee, because it is of equal significance with the Lord's day, for the reason already alleged concerning it.³⁰

If during the earliest church history the 'day of the Lord' did refer to Easter Sunday, its naming harmonizes conceptually with the content of Easter, on which day, in addition to Christ's resurrection, His glorious appearance before the Father is commemorated. This is why Dugmore argues:

What day could be more fitting for him to experience a vision of the Risen and Glorified Christ? It is most significant that the description of our Lord in Rev. i 14 is in terms of the traditional Jewish picture of the Almighty, taken from the vision of the 'ancient of days' of Dan. viii 9.³¹

²² Nicholas the Lyra et al., *Biblior u m sacror u mc u m glossa ordinaria, t om u s sext u s* (Venetiis: Gasparis Trechsel, 1601), ad corinthios, col. 351.

²³ Augustine, "Epistola XXXVI,XI,29" in *PL, tomus XXXIII, tomus secundus*, ed. J.-P. Migne (Parisina: J.-P. Migne, 1865), col. 150.

²⁴ Dugmore, C.W., "Lord's Day and Easter" in *Oscar Cullmann Festchrift volume Neotestamentica et Patristica* "Supplements to Novum Testamentum", vol. 6. (Leiden: Brill, 1962),274. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004265837_025.

²⁵ Ibid.

²⁶ Ibid., 276.

²⁷ Kenneth A. Strand, "Another Look at the Lord's Day in the Early Church and Rev. 1:10" in *NTS 13* (1967), 177. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0028688500018269>.

²⁸ κυριακῆ; *Dominico Die*.

²⁹ περὶ τοῦ Πάσχα.

³⁰ Fragments from the Lost Writings of Irenæus' in ANF, 1, 569-570. Greek: Internet Archive, "Sancti Irenæi", accessed 27 visited 2021, <https://archive.org/details/sanctiirenaei00harvgoog/page/n488/mode/2up>.

³¹ Dugmore, *Lord's Day and Easter*, 277.

PART 1: TRANSLATION HISTORY

Introduction and design

This section examines the translation of the phrase *κατὰ μίαν σαββάτων* in historical Bibles to determine time and place of the translation change. This part of the diachronic analysis thus focuses on the form.

This research must necessarily be limited in terms of geographic spread and languages. First, to limit the size of the study. And second, for substantive reasons. Because Luther translated this phrase differently than, for example, the King James Version, focusing on the Western European language area during the Reformation makes sense. Further, a limitation to the Latin Church is defensible. Broadening the scope to include translations by the Orthodox or Coptic Churches would introduce methodological complications due to differences in source text families, distinct theological approaches, and the aftermath of the schism of 1054.

The multitude of Bibles published after the introduction of printing further necessitated the use of sampling. Included in the set were 131 historical Bibles for which a photographic reproduction or facsimile was available, since relying on 'transcripts of original versions' was found to be potential misleading.³² The methodology followed, employing an extensive and randomly selected set of datapoints from primary sources, yielded a representative and trustworthy result.

Results (overview)

The research results are included as a table in Appendix 1, which also has bibliographic data of the 131 consulted manuscripts and Bible editions. Due to the specific purpose of this section, a summary is provided here:³³

- Before 1560 there is homogeneity between the different translations. Verse 1 Cor. 16:2^a was universally translated with variations of 'each one of the sabbaths/weeks'.
- Footnotes in various Bibles show that 1 Cor. 16:2 was quite commonly understood as referring to an ingathering on the weekly Sunday.
- The earliest translations rendering it as 'every first day of the week' were the Geneva Bible and Beza's Latin translation (both from 1560).³⁴
- After 1560 the translation gradually changed to 'Every first day of the week' or 'every Sunday' with the quickest changes seen within Calvinist-influenced translations.

³² Biblegateway, "1 Corinthians 16...", visited 8 October 2021, <https://www.biblegateway.com/passage/?search=1+Korinther+16&version=LUTH1545> shows 'jeglichem ersten Tag der Woche' but the original contains 'einen jeglights Sabbather'.

³³ See Appendix 1 for full details.

³⁴ Theoretically, the Vorsterman Bible (1531) could be an exception because the Old Dutch 'nae' means both 'to' and 'after' (such is the case in: 'Hier nae volcht dat Euangelium van Sinte Ioannes' which is translated: 'here *after* follows the Gospel of Saint John'). However, the meaning 'after' is unlikely given the multiple use of 'nae' in the sense of 'to' in the direct context of 1 Cor. 16:2 (i.e. 1 Cor. 3:2, 3:10, 10:18 and 15:23).

- German and Catholic translations (such as the 'Dietenberger Bibel') made this change to 'first day of the week' considerably later. For example, the Luther translation introduced this translation change around 1900.
- The 'per unam sabbati' in Clementines Vulgaat (1592) changed only very recently with the publication of the Neo-Vulgaat (1979) to 'per primam sabbati'.³⁵

Conclusion of part 1

This part of the study found a sharp tipping point in the translation of *κατὰ μίαν σαββάτων* around 1560 in Geneva. After this, the fundamentally new translation form 'first day of the week' appeared, starting with Bibles from the Calvinist movement.

The observed homogeneity in translation until 1560 suggests uniformity of understanding before that change. This is unlikely. Although strictly speaking, the Latin *sabbatum*, as transliteration of the intermediate Greek *Σάββατο*, singularly refers to שַׁבָּת (≈ Saturday), it had gradually taken on additional meanings, including "Christian Sabbath" (= Sunday) and "week." This broadening of meaning also affected the target languages of the translations. Hence, the meaning appropriated to 'Sabbath' determined the ultimate understanding of the translated idiom. The change to 'every first day of the week' removed this ambiguity, produced an unambiguous understanding, and masked the underlying enigmatic Greek idiom.

³⁵ Interestingly, in Clementine's Vulgate the Latin 'sabbati' is meant to be understood as 'Sunday', but in the Neo-Vulgate as 'week'.

PART 2: THE HISTORICAL CONTEXT OF THE CHANGE

Introduction and design

Any translation process involves reformulating texts from a source language into a target language. This process includes an exegesis of the source text, which is strongly influenced by the presence of key terms and the use of idioms. Although these are fixed in morphological form, the attributed meaning of any given term can change over time. The prelude showed such a shift in the understanding of key terms, even among early commentators. The change in form in the target language(s), however, only took place in Geneva in 1560. Therefore, this part of the research focuses mainly on that period.

Reformational reformulation

Desiderius Erasmus

Motivated by the humanistic *Zeitgeist* to go *ad fontes*, Desiderius Erasmus published his *Novum Instrumentum omne* on March 6, 1516.³⁶ This edition contained the first printed Greek text of the New Testament, based on the source manuscripts available to him.³⁷ Additionally, this work, which he faithfully dedicated to Pope Leo X, also contained a new Latin translation. Because Erasmus' Latin translation differed from the Vulgate, it aroused discussion, catalyzing the budding Reformation. Of interest to this research is the archbishop's critique,³⁸ as it was transmitted by Erasmus' bosom friend Thomas More³⁹ in letter 472 dated 31 October 1516:

He is delighted with your version of the New Testament, in which however he thinks you have been more scrupulous than he would wish. He does not like your (sic) having left the word Sabbath, and some others of the kind, which you either did not think it expedient or did not venture to alter, whereas he does not admit any expression at all, which would be strange to Roman ears. I approved his judgment so far as the Hebrew rites and practices would admit. For the rest I advised him to send you a list of the words which he would like to have translated differently, with his judgment about them, and this I think he will do.⁴⁰

A little further on follows a clear reminder to pay attention to next releases of his Latin translation:

I do beg and beseech you to lose no time in revising and correcting the whole, so as to leave the smallest possible room for calumny anywhere, for which some very shrewd persons are not only determined to find out every occasion, but will seize it with pleasure and avidity.⁴¹

³⁶ Desiderius Erasmus (trans.), *Novum Instrumentum omne: diligenter ab Erasmo Roterodamo recognitum ...* (Zurich: Johannes Froben, 1516).

³⁷ According to 'uerumetiam ad multorum utriusquæ linguæ codicum' in *ibid.*, title page.

³⁸ Probably this is a reference to Archbishop William Warham of Canterbury, based upon the mention of his secretary Thomas Bedill.

³⁹ About 280 letters were written back and forth. While staying with More, Erasmus authored his famous book 'In Praise of Folly'.

⁴⁰ Desiderius Erasmus, *The Epistles of Erasmus*, Vol. 2, trans. F.M. Nichols (London: Longmans, Green & Co., 1904), 425.

⁴¹ *Ibid.*

This seemed to also had effect on the translation of *κατὰ μίαν σαββάτων*. Erasmus translated it in 1516 as “in una fabbato”⁴² to which he added the following annotation: “id est fabbatorum,”⁴³ but in 1519 he translated it only as “in una fabbatorum.”⁴⁴ That the translation of this idiom was not obvious, is apparent from the further course: in 1522 he translated it into “in vna fabbaton,”⁴⁵ in 1527 into “in una fabbatorū”⁴⁶ and finally in 1535 as “in una fabbatorum.”⁴⁷ It is also clear from his commentary published in 1535 that Erasmus was influenced by earlier commentators:

σαββάτων, that is, *Sabbatorum*. Theophylactus notes that "one" is said to mean "first," and that it signifies the Lord's Day, in which Chrysostom agrees.⁴⁸

Martin Luther

Luther's legendary 95 theses (1517) gave momentum to the nascent Reformation, but at the same time evoked opposing forces. Crucial was the Leipzig Disputation (1519) between Martin Luther and Dr. Johannes Eck, a Catholic prelate.⁴⁹ A major point of contention was the authority of the Pope, which Luther subordinated to the *sola scriptura*. According to Eck, the abolition of the Sabbath (and the institution of holy days commemorating saints) rested on ecclesiastical authority and did not follow from Scripture. Consistency required that the Reformers "should keep the Sabbath like the Jews."⁵⁰ Luther's inability to refute this was then widely exploited by Eck in his highly influential booklet *Enchiridion*. Permanently rejecting Saints' Days, Luther, a year after the dispute, still partly capitulated to Eck, by instructing to “make sure that man rejects all feast days and only preserves the Sunday.”⁵¹

In Luther's case, however, there seems to be no formal transfer from Sabbath to Sunday, since Luther declares in his catechism that “for Christians it is free [to

⁴² Desiderius Erasmus (trans.), *Novum Instrumentum* (1516), Epistolae Pavli Apostoli, 55.

⁴³ Ibid., Anotationum, 482.

⁴⁴ Desiderius Erasmus (trans.), *Novum Testamentum omne, multo quàm antehac diligentius ab Erasmo Roterodamo* (Basileae: Johannes Froben, 1519), 379.

⁴⁵ Desiderius Erasmus (trans.), *Novum testamentum omne: tertio iam ac diligentius ab Erasmo Roterodamo recognitum* (Basileae: Pamphili Gengenbachii, 1522), 441.

⁴⁶ Desiderius Erasmus, *Ioannes Frobenius candido lectori sd en Novum Testamentum, ex Erasmi Roterodami recognitione* (Basileae: Johannes Froben, 1527), 372.

⁴⁷ Desiderius Erasmus (trans.), *Novi Testamenti aeditio postrema ...* (Basileæ: officina Frobeniana, 1535), 478.

⁴⁸ Desiderius Erasmus, *Des Erasmi Roterdami In Novvm Testamentvm Annotationes...* (Basileæ: officina Frobeniana, 1535), 520. The provided text is my own English translation of the original Latin text: *σαββάτων*. id est, Sabbatorum. Theophylactus admonet Vnam, dictam esse pro Primam: significari autem diem dominicum. in quo consentit Chrysoftomus.

⁴⁹ For a (rather biased) impression see W.H.T. Dau, *The Leipzig debate in 1519: leaves from the story of Luther's life* (St. Louis: Concordia Pub. House, 1919).

⁵⁰ J.N. Andrews & L.R., Conradi, *History of the Sabbath and the first day of the week*, 4th edition (Washington: Review & Herald Publishing Association, 1912), 586-587.

⁵¹ Martin Luther, *An der Christlichen Adel deutscher Nation* (Leipzig: Valentin Schumann, 1520), 45th pp. The provided English text is my own translation of the German original: "Zum achtzehenden das man alle fest abethet vnnd allein den Sontag behielt."

choose] a feast day.”⁵² He did not propagate a strict Sunday rest but pragmatically stated:

(...) at least select one day in the week. Since from times past the Sunday has been set apart for this, so shall man stick to this, so that all will take place in right order, and nobody will create chaos by unnecessary novelties.⁵³

Luther based his influential German Bible translation on Erasmus's Greek text of 1519, which, because of Beza, later became known as the *Textus Receptus*. Like seen earlier with Erasmus, there was variation in the translation of the *κατα μιαν σαββατων*, but Luther kept steadfast to a 'word for word' translation: in 1522 as “auff iah der Sabbather eynen,”⁵⁴ in 1524 as “auf der Sabather einen,”⁵⁵ in 1530 as “Auf der Sabbathen einen”⁵⁶ and in 1545 as “Auf einen jegchten sabbather.”⁵⁷

Augsburg Confession

Eck's *Enchiridion* meanwhile experienced many reprints, which resulted in further polarization. The question of church authority was linked to the shift from Sabbath to Sunday, with the exponent of the Counter-Reformation aiming high:

The Sabbath has been commanded in many ways in the scripture. Nowhere in the Gospel, in Paul, or in the entire Bible is it stated that the Sabbath has been abolished and Sunday instituted. Therefore, this has been done by the institution of the Apostolic Church, without scripture.

If the church had the authority to transfer the Sabbath, which is in the scripture, to Sunday, and to command that Sunday be observed, why should it not have the authority over other days as well? (...) If you rely solely on the scripture from the church, then you must observe the Sabbath with the Jews, which has been kept since the beginning of the world.⁵⁸

⁵² Martin Luther, *Deutsch Catechismus: Mit einer neuen vorrhede, vnd vermanunge zu der Beicht* ([Wittenberg]: [George Rhaw], 1531), XXVI-left. The provided English text is my own translation of the German original: “feyertag frey bey den Christen.”

⁵³ The provided English text is my own translation of the German original: “(...) zum wenigsten einen tag inn der woche dazu aufschieffen. [= auswählen] Weil aber von alters her der Sontag dazu gefellet ift, sol mans auch dabey bleiben lassen, auff das es inn eintrechtiger ordnung gehe, und niemand durch unnottige newrung ein unordnung mache” in Luther, *Deutsch Catechism*, XXVI-right.

⁵⁴ Martin Luther (übers.), *Das Neue Testament Deutzsch* (Wittenberg: Melchior Lotter, 1522), no page numbers.

⁵⁵ Martin Luther (übers.), *Das gantz Nüw Testament...* (Zurich: Johannem Hager, 1524), 529.

⁵⁶ Martin Luther (übers.), *Neues Testament. Deutsch* (Zurich: Christoph Froschauer, 1530), 540.

⁵⁷ Martin Luther (übers.), *Die Bibel oder die ganze Heilige Schrift*, LXXXVI. auflage (Halle: Cansteinischen Bibel-Anstalt, 1784), 213.

⁵⁸ Johannes Eck, *Enchiridion Handbüchlinn gemayner...* (Ingolstadt: Alexander Weißenhorn, 1530), folio 79left-79right. The provided English text is my own translation of the German original: “Der Sabath ift manigfeltigtlich gebotten worden in der gefchrifft/ Nun ifts weder im Euagelio/ noch in paulo oder in der ganntzen Bybel/ das der Sabath auffgehept fey/ und der Sontag eingefetzt/ darumb ift dat gefchehen von einfatzung der Apoftolifchen kirchen/on gefchrifft. Hat nun die kirch macht gehabt den Sabbat/ der inn der gefchrifft ift/ umb zülegen auff den Sontag, und den Sontag zü bieten zü feyren/ warumb

Elaborating strongly on Luther's ideas, Philip Melancthon has formulated in *Die Augsburgische Confession* a retort to this:

Thus, one should observe Sunday, Easter, Pentecost, and similar ordinances. For the church has not abolished or repealed the Sabbath, but God Himself has taught that we are not bound to the law of Moses in the New Testament. Therefore, the apostles have dropped the Sabbath (...).⁵⁹

It is striking that a reference to 1 Cor. 16:2 is missing here to support this 'dropping' of the Shabbat. Only after the translation change to 'first day of the week' became commonplace did this verse become widely used as a proof text within apologetic writings surrounding the Sabbath versus Sunday controversy.

John Calvin

Like Luther, Calvin regarded the 'old Sabbath' as a typological image fulfilled in Christ's resurrection.⁶⁰ With no superstition involved, the day of meeting did not matter,⁶¹ so that, to him, even the 'setting apart' of the Saturday could be legitimate. This follows from his commentary on the Corinthian ingathering which Calvin apparently places on the Sabbath:

This preposterous distinction of days the Apostle strenuously opposes; and not that legitimate difference which promotes the peace of the Christian Church. For in the churches which he founded, the sabbath was retained for this purpose. He prescribes the same day to the Corinthians, for making collections for the relief of the brethren at Jerusalem. If superstition be an object of fear, there was more danger in the holy days of the Jews, than in the Lord's days now observed by Christians.⁶²

Also noteworthy from Calvin's commentary on 1 Cor. 16 is that he understood Chrysostom as referring to 'primo sabbatho':

The clause rendered on one of the Sabbaths, (κατὰ μίαν σαββάτων ,) Chrysostom explains to mean — the first Sabbath. In this I do not agree with him; for Paul

wolte ly nit das macht haben in andern tagen auch/ (...) / [?] fall von der kirchen an die bloffe gefchrift/ so muftu den Sabath halten mit den Juden/ der vomm annbeginn der welt/ ift gehalten worden.“

⁵⁹ [Philip Melancthon], *Confessio odder Bekantnus des Glaubens...* ([Wittenberg]: [Rhou], 1530), Article XXVIII. The provided English text is my own translation of the German original: “Also sol man von Sontag/ Ostern Pffingsten/ und dergeigen/ ordnung halten/ Denn die kirch hat de Sabbat nicht verrücht oder auffgehoben/ sondern Gott hat selbst geleret/ das wir im newen Testament nicht sollen verbunden sein zum gesetz Mosi/ Darümb haben die Apostel den Sabbat fallen lassen (...).“

⁶⁰ “quam vetus sabbatum adumbrabat, in resurrectione Domini finis sit ac complementum”, John Calvin, “Institutio 2.8.34” in John Calvin, *Institutio Christianae religionis*, Vol. 1 (Berolini: Gustavum Eichler, 1834), 260.

⁶¹ “neque enim ecclesias damnvero, quae alios conventibus suis sollennes dies habeant, modo a superstitione absinthe” in *ibid.*

⁶² Calvin, “Institutio 2.8.33” in *ibid.* The Latin text reads “In hanc, inquam, praeposteram dierum discretionem invehitur Apostolus: non in legitimum delectum, qui societatis Christianae paci serviat. Siquidem in ecclesiis ab eo institutis sabbatum in hunc usum retinebatur. Illum enim diem praescribit Corinthiis, quo symbola ad sublevandos Hierosolymitanos fratres colligantur. Si timetur superstitio, plus erat periculi in Iudaicis feriis, quam in Dominicis (quos nunc habent Christiani) diebus”. The provided English translation is by John Allen (1813) and taken from Project Gutenberg available via <https://www.gutenberg.org/cache/epub/45001/pg45001-images.html#toc77>.

means rather that they should contribute, one on one Sabbath and another on another; or even each of them every Sabbath, if they chose.⁶³

It is also significant that (this quote shows that Calvin was of the opinion that Chrysostom meant that)⁶⁴ *κατὰ μίαν σαββάτων* is not understood as repetitive but as a 'one-off.' This implies that (according to Calvin's understanding of Chrysostom, to the latter) the resurrection verses refer singularly to Easter Sunday (≈ day of the Wave Sheaf Offering)⁶⁵ and not to weekly Sundays. Calvin's familiarity with Chrysostom is further shown by his many handwritten notes in his copy of Chrysostom's Homilies. Considering this study, Calvin's underlining in *Joan. Hom. XI* is remarkable.⁶⁶ Chrysostom here writes *κατὰ μίαν σαββάτων, ἢ καὶ κατὰ σάββατον*, (later) translated to Latin as 'ut unu dierum in hebdomade, vel saltem sabbato'.⁶⁷ Here too, the idiom *μίαν σαββάτων* was not translated as 'first day of the week'.

A complication to any proper reconstruction is that Calvin also used *sabbatum* in a functional way (as a day of rest and teaching) to indicate Sunday.⁶⁸ In line with a theocracy, Calvin abolished all other holy days except Sunday, which he observed with the strictness of the 'Jewish' Sabbath.⁶⁹

Theodore Beza

Beza's '*Nova Interpret'* (1560),⁷⁰ the Latin translation of Erasmus second Greek text edition, was a novelty in the translation of *κατὰ μίαν σαββάτων*. As Calvin's successor in 1564, Beza shared much of his thinking, but was more outspoken on 1 Cor. 16:2:

We say that it is a superstition to esteem one day more holy than another, (...) But, following what the Lord has commanded, we sanctify one of the seven days (Gen 2:3). We devote it entirely to ecclesiastical assemblies to hear the Word of God; yet, as we have said, there is with us no Judaistic ceremony or stupid superstition.

⁶³ John Calvin, "opera quae supersunt omnia" in *Corpus reformationum, Tome 49*, ed. Edouard Cunitz (Brunsvigæ: CA Schwetschke, 1863), col. 566. The Latin original: "Particulam hanc *κατὰ μίαν σαββάτων* exponit Chrysostomus primo sabbatho: cui ego non assentior. Potius enim significat Paulus, ut conferant hic uno sabbatho, alius alio: (...)." The provided English text is taken from Calvin's Commentary on the Bible for 1 Cor. 16 available via <https://www.studydrive.net/commentaries/eng/cal/1-corinthians-16.html>.

⁶⁴ The text in brackets is inserted in this translation for clarification.

⁶⁵ Ibid.

⁶⁶ Alexandre Ganoczy & Klaus Müller, *Calvin's handschriftliche Annotationen zu Chrysostomus: ein Beitrag zur Hermeneutik Calvins* (Wiesbaden: Franz Steiner Verlag, 1981), 100. Available via: <https://archive.org/details/calvinhandschri0000gano/page/100/mode/2up>.

⁶⁷ Additional information, not provided in the original thesis: the included Latin translation was taken from *Calvin's handschriftliche Annotationen*. Other Latin translations are available: <https://www.clioproject.net/homilies/comparison.php?page=11.1.3>.

⁶⁸ As evidenced by his letters. For example, letter CCLXXXIII to Bullinger in: John Calvin, *Letters of John Calvin*, Vol. 2, ed. J. Bonnet (Bellingham: Logos Bible Software, 2009), 305.

⁶⁹ Calvin, "Institutio 2.8.28" in Calvin, *Institutio Christianae*, Vol. 1, 257-258.

⁷⁰ Theodore Beza (trans.), *Tes kaines diathekes hapanta, Novum DN Jesu Christi will* _ (Basileae: Nicolaus Barbirius, 1560).

This is why we have not chosen the Jewish Sabbath, Saturday, but Sunday, following the custom of the early Church (1 Cor 16:2; Acts 20:7; Rev 1:10).⁷¹

Convinced that 1 Cor. 16:2 referred to 'first day of the week', Beza was the first to unambiguously translate this as "Primo quoque *die* hebdomadis,"⁷² thereby removing the dubious term *sabbatum*. Incidentally, his annotation in this edition still refers to the Greek source text, the Vulgate and Erasmus's Latin translation. Leaving behind the concordant 'word for word' translation, Beza was the first to apply the dynamically equivalent translation principle, long before this term was introduced. He brought the text in line with how (most) reformers understood and applied it.

The Geneva Bible

Beza's revolutionary new translation gained momentum because Geneva had become a haven for Britons with reformatory sympathies, who were persecuted by Bloody Mary by fire and sword. With Beza's cooperation, the Geneva Bible was published in 1560 and would eventually become immensely popular in England. In line with Beza's Latin translation, *κατὰ μίαν σαββάτων* was translated as "Euerie first day of the week,"⁷³ with which this formulation first reached the public. Eventually, the Geneva Bible would sail on the Mayflower to the New World.

The King James Version

The controversy between Puritans and Anglicans brought England to the brink of religious civil war around 1600. In 1603, after 36 years of Scottish kingship, James I became King of England. At Puritan's suggestion, to promote unity, he commissioned a new Bible translation that later became known as the KJV. Instructed by James, Archbishop Richard Bancroft established the translation principles, including preserving "Old Ecclesiastical Words."⁷⁴ The starting point for the revision was the Bishops' Bible, supplemented by five other translations if they corresponded more closely to the source texts.⁷⁵ In this revision, Beza's translation carried considerable weight.⁷⁶ As a result, the immensely popular *Geneva Bible* left its mark on the KJV⁷⁷ and also provided the final translation for *κατὰ μίαν σαββάτων*. The authorization by 'The Empire on which the sun never sets' ensured that Beza's innovation eventually became commonplace.

⁷¹ Theodore Beza, *The Christian Faith*, trans. James Clark (East Sussex: Christian Focus Ministries Trust, 1992), 107–8.

⁷² Beza, *kaines diathekes hapanta*, 565.

⁷³ *The Bible and Holy Scriptvres conteyned in the olde and newe teltament* (Geneva: 1560), Rouland Hall, without page numbering.

⁷⁴ Isaac Hollister Hall, *The revised New Testament and history of revision* (Philadelphia: Hubbard Bros., 1881), 43.

⁷⁵ *Ibid*, 45.

⁷⁶ F.H.A. Scrivener, *The authorized edition of the English Bible (1611), its subsequent reprints and modern representatives* (Cambridge: The University press, 1884), 57.

⁷⁷ Bruce Metzger, "The Geneva Bible of 1560" in *Theology Today*, v17 n3 (1960): 346. <https://doi.org/10.1177/004057366001700308>.

Conclusion of part 2

The research results show that the translation change is the visible capstone formed from a preceding *umdeutung*. The textual change turned out, ironically a side effect of the reformational adage *sola scriptura*. With a wide distribution of the Word in the vernacular among 'the common people', in combination with a highly polarized environment, 'incomprehensible constructions with the word sabbath' would lead to problems. This, coupled with strict Sunday observance, pushed the Genevan Reformers to overcome the discrepancy between *praxis* and *scriptura*. Even though this was a grateful farewell to 'forms that sounded too Jewish', this change of form was probably not experienced as a change of meaning and was therefore considered justified.

PART 3: THE SENSUS LITERALIS AS A SENSIBLE EXEGESIS

Introduction and design

The outcome of sub-question 1 shows one and a half millennia of great similarity of form between source and target languages for the idiom *μίαν σαββάτων*. The current *communis opinio* is that this idiom means 'first day of the week' on grammatical grounds. However, the earliest translators wrote analogous idioms in their target languages rather than unambiguous references to Sunday.⁷⁸ This suggests that, at that time, this idiom in the target language had meaningful content distinct from "first day of the week." If this was indeed the case, then the translation change in 1560 was not only a change of form but also a change of content.

To gain hermeneutical insight into how *κατὰ μίαν σαββάτων* might have been understood at the time of Paul, *close reading* is necessary. The starting point is the plural form because earlier research showed that this form was seen as normative from the early church fathers until the Reformation.⁷⁹ The first part of this point-by-point reconstruction concerns an intertextual investigation. The second part will deal with grammatical aspects.

Intertextuality

The spring festivals in Corinthians

If the *μίαν σαββάτων* in 1 Cor. 16:2 indeed (in some way) relate to the Omer Period, it is plausible — but not required — that the Corinthian Epistle also contains other textual references to the Biblical spring festivals. An attentive reading of the letter yields the following list of references to the Biblical spring festivals:

- 2:7-8 - Crucifixion of Christ, the mystery of God predestined (Pesach).
- 2:12 - Receiving the Spirit from God (Feast of Weeks).
- 5:6 - A little leaven (Unleavened Bread).
- 5:7 – Christ, our Passover lamb, has been slain (Pesach).
- 5:8 - Instruction to celebrate Unleavened Bread with sincerity and truth.
- 10:1-2 - All by the sea, all baptized into Moses (last day of Unleavened Bread).⁸⁰
- 11:23-26 - Description of the 'Last Supper' (day before Pesach).
- 15:3 - The death of Christ as foretold in the scriptures (Pesach).
- 15:4&20 - Risen on the third day (Wave Sheaf Offering).
- 16:8 - Pentecost (Feast of Weeks).

⁷⁸ The usual medieval method of translation was a mechanical word-for-word translation.

⁷⁹ This plural form has good early text witnesses: \aleph (cor.), B(distigme) and *Basil Morals* 48,6. See also appendix 2.

⁸⁰ Michael A. Daise elaborates this Red Sea narrative schematically and places 1 Cor. 10:1-4 between Pesach and the Feast of Weeks. In: Michael A. Daise, "Christ Our Passover" (1 Corinthians 5:6–8) The Death of Jesus and the Quartodeciman Passover" in *Neotestamentica*, Vol. 50, no. 2, New Testament Society of Southern Africa (2016), 519. <https://doi.org/10.1353/neo.2016.0056>.

The presence of ten references to the biblical spring⁸¹ festivals also rationalize alertness to allusions to the same. Such allusions abound, especially about Unleavened Bread, which encapsulates the day of the Wave Sheaf Offering. For example, *φυσιόω* is used figuratively six times within the Corinthian Epistle.⁸² The *ἐξάλρω* in 1 Cor. 5:2 and 5:13 form an *inclusio* around the command to celebrate the feast of Unleavened Bread. The command to 'remove evil from among you' is analogous to the instruction in Ex.13:7 to remove all conjecture.⁸³ Because of the many references (and allusions) to the biblical spring feasts within the First Corinthian Epistle, it makes sense to make these festivals part of the hermeneutical key.

Collection instruction timeline

Although a precise date or time of year is impossible to determine, there are indications that Paul probably wrote this letter in the early spring.

The place of composition of 1 Corinthians is clearly Ephesus, as Paul states in 16:8. The same verse indicates that the letter was composed in or near springtime, as Paul is awaiting Pentecost at Ephesus, yet plans to journey to Corinth and perhaps to winter there (16:6). Beyond the time of year, 1 Corinthians gives us no further specific information about its date of composition.⁸⁴

Because Paul indicates that he plans to arrive after Pentecost, the period within which the one-off ingathering must take place is limited from 'sometime before Pesach' to 'sometime after Pentecost', which includes at least the Omer Period.⁸⁵

Intertextuality with LXX

Surpassed only by Romans, Paul appeals to the Scriptures exceptionally often in the first Corinthian Epistle. This is shown by his tenfold usage of a form of *γέγραπται*.⁸⁶ Twice Paul emphasizes that the crucifixion and resurrection of Christ happened *κατὰ τὰς γραφὰς*⁸⁷ suggesting that the Tanakh provided the blueprint for the complete *Passio Jesu Christi*. Hence, it is likely that Wave Sheaf Offering, because of its connection with Pesach and its being an antetype for the exaltation of Christ, is integral to this. Incidentally, the Tanakh functions as a frame of reference for the Corinthian Epistle in several ways:

⁸¹ 1 Cor. also hints at the fall feasts which function in complementarity: 15:53 (possibly referring to the Day of Trumpets) and 16:22^b (*μαρναναθά*, when understood as 'our Lord, come!').

⁸² 1 Cor. 4:6&18&19, 5:2, 8:1 and 13:4. In addition, it only occurs in the NT in Col. 2:18.

⁸³ *יָרָוּעַ*.

⁸⁴ Hans D. Betz & Margaret M. Mitchell, "Corinthians, First Epistle to the" in *The Anchor Yale Bible Dictionary*, Vol. 1, ed. D. N. Freedman (New York: Doubleday, 1992), 1140.

⁸⁵ From 2 Cor. 8:6 shows that this project 'has been lying still' while from 2 Cor. 8:10 and 9:2 it is clear that this concerned a period of 1 year (*ἀπὸ πέρυσι*). With that, the restart of the collection would also be in the spring.

⁸⁶ 1 Cor. 1:19&31, 2:9, 3:19, 9:9&10, 10:7&11 and 15:45&54 (4:6 does not introduce a quote).

⁸⁷ 1 Cor. 15:3&4 quoted in CCC 652. CCC refers to *Catechism of the Catholic Church*. The English text is available via https://www.vatican.va/archive/ENG0015/_INDEX.HTM.

Ciampa and Rosner also discuss the role of the Old Testament in 1 Corinthians. There are 18 citations from or allusions to Old Testament material found within the letter. Many of these come from the books of Deuteronomy and Isaiah. Other less explicit references to Scripture have also been noted within the book, and thus, a greater amount of Jewish influence may be seen than previously acknowledged.⁸⁸

Intertextuality with the LXX is therefore to be expected. The ingathering instruction appears to be modeled on Deut. 16:10. In the εὐδοῶται of 1 Cor. 16:2 is an echo of the καθότι ηὐλόγησέν σε κύριος ὁ θεός σου in Deut. 16:10^p (LXX). This verse describes bringing a voluntary offering during the Feast of Weeks. Accounts of one-off and voluntary collections in the Tanakh are often connected to the Feast of Weeks (e.g., Ex. 25:1-7, 2 Chron. 31, Baruch 1:6). Given that the supposed closing moment of the ingathering commanded by 1 Cor. 16:1-4 was Pentecost, it follows these historical precedents.

Collection as offering of the First Fruits

Paul refers to the ingathering in 1 Cor. 16:1 as λογείας, a Biblical *hapax legomenon* but known from the Greek Ostracas of Egypt and Nubia.⁸⁹ This gives the collection a cultic undertone. Paul mentions in Rom. 15:25-28 the ingathering 'fruit' (καρπὸν), which connects it with the language field of the firstfruits (ἀπαρχή)⁹⁰ and therefore also with the Wave Sheaf Offering, as an assurance that the entire harvest will surely be gathered.⁹¹ Within the Pentateuch (with the exception of Deut. 33:21) every occurrence of ἀπαρχή has a cultic connotation.⁹² Also Didache 13:3-4 suggests a connection between the term ἀπαρχήν and the offering of the firstfruits, here intended to benefit the prophet. However, if no prophet is available, the offering must be given to the poor.⁹³

Noteworthy is Paul's use of ἀπαρχή in 1 Cor. 16:15 to describe the household of Stephen.⁹⁴ In 1 Cor. 15:20 and 15:23 ἀπαρχή is used for Christ as the firstfruits. As a personal description (other than to designate Christ), this only occurs more frequently in the Pauline corpus in Rom. 16:5 where Epenetus is called 'firstfruits of Christ from Asia'.⁹⁵ As in the Corinthians letter, this is near a passage concerning

⁸⁸ D. Williams, "Corinthians, First Letter to the" in *The Lexham Bible Dictionary*, ed. W. Widder et al. (Bellingham: Lexham Press, 2016), electronic, no page numbers.

⁸⁹ 'Vgl. die zahlreichen Belege aus Papyri und Inschriften auch im Sinne sakraler Geldsammlungen bei Kittel, ThWNT IV 285f und Bauer/Aland 965. Das begründet aber nicht die These, auch an unserer Stelle sei »die kultisch-sakrale Komponente« betont ...' in Wolfgang Schrage, *Der erste Letter an die Korinther VII/4, Evangelisch Katholischer Kommentar zum neuen Testament* (Düsseldorf: Benziger, 2001), 425.

⁹⁰ Hebrew: אַפְרָחִים or אַפְרָחִים.

⁹¹ Compare 1 Cor. 15:23 and Rom. 11:16.

⁹² LXX: Ex. 22:28, 23:19, 25:2&3, 35:5, 36:6, 39:1, Lev. 2:12, 22:12, 23:10, Num. 5:9; 15:20&21, 18:8&11&12&29&30&32, 31:29, Deut. 12:6&11&17, 18:4, 26:2&10.

⁹³ Kurt Niederwimmer, *Die Didache* (Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 1989), 232.

⁹⁴ The term ἀπαρχή may also have been used in a functional manner: (...) they appointed their firstfruits (ἀπαρχας), who when confirmed by the Spirit, were ordained as bishops and deacons (1 Clement 42:2).

⁹⁵ Variant reading MSS: from Achaia.

the ingathering. The thrice use of ἀπαρχή in the Corinthian letter⁹⁶ — positioned around the collection section — is striking and forms an *inclusio*.

Going into detail about the theological significance of the ingathering for Paul is too extensive for this thesis.⁹⁷ However, Wolfgang Schrage also noticed a possible layer of meaning that fits well with the concepts of ἀπαρχή and καρπὸν:

"(...) even a connection with the eschatological expectation (...), referring particularly to the motif of the end-time pilgrimage of nations to Jerusalem or Zion (cf. Isaiah 2:2-5, Micah 4:1-3)."⁹⁸

If this eschatological dimension is indeed present, it strengthens the connection between 1 Cor. 16:1-4 and the previous chapter.

Connection between chapters 15 and 16

Contrary to what the blank line between 1 Cor. 15 and 16 suggests, there is a firm connection between these chapters. Chrysostom already made this point in his homily *περὶ ἐλεημοσύνης*,⁹⁹ in which he emphasized the connection between resurrection and ingathering:

Behold the intelligence of the Apostle, how opportune his advice. In other words, when he called to mind the future court and that fearful tribunal, and the glory with which the righteous will be clothed, and the immortal way of life, then he inserted this speech about the poor, so that the one who listens will become optimistic and docile,¹⁰⁰

Even stronger seems the connection between the exhortation of 1 Cor. 15:58¹⁰¹ and the practical instructions in 1 Cor. 16:1-4. as also emphasized by John Lightfoot:

The word *θησαυρίζων*,¹⁰² may perhaps intimate that money thus appropriated is not lost, but is *treasured up* against the final day of retribution. So Eccles. 11:1. "Cast thy bread-corn upon the waters, and thou shalt find it after many days."¹⁰³

The existence of this strong connection between chapters 15 and 16 is relevant because it makes plausible to interpret the *μίαν σαββάτων* in 1 Cor. 16:2^a in connection with Christ's resurrection. William Kay describes this as follows: "The

⁹⁶ 1 Cor. 15:2&23, 16:15.

⁹⁷ This was by no means an afterthought for Paul: Acts 11:27–30&24:17, Rom. 15:25–28; 1 Cor. 16:1-4, 2 Cor. 8:1–9:15; Gal. 2:10.

⁹⁸ In: Schrage, *Korinther VII/4*, 426. The provided text is my own translation of the German original: „(...) sogar einen Zusammenhang mit der eschatologischen Erwartung (...), wobei vor allem auf das Motiv der endzeitlichen Völkerwallfahrt nach Jerusalem bzw. zum Zion verwiesen wird (vgl. Jes. 2:2-5, Mi 4:1-3).“ To which Schrage commented: "Ob der eschatologische Bezug auch an unsere Stelle mitzuhören ist, bleibt zwar ungewiß". (translation: "Whether the eschatological reference can also be heard in our passage remains uncertain.").

⁹⁹ John Chrysostom, *On Repentance and Almsgiving*, Vol. 96, ed. TP Halton, trans. G. G. Christo (Washington: The Catholic University of America Press, 1998), xvi.

¹⁰⁰ *Ibid.*, 133.

¹⁰¹ On syntactical grounds (by the "Ὡστε in 1 Cor. 15:58) rhetorically strongly connected with the preceding section.

¹⁰² In 1 Cor. 16:2.

¹⁰³ William Lothian, *Expository Lectures on Paul's Epistles to the Corinthians* (Edinburgh: Waugh & Innes, 1828), 340.

expression used in the account of the Resurrection – very suitable after the exposition in xv.”¹⁰⁴

Other uses of *μίαν σαββάτων* in NT

According to the usual translations the expression 'first day of the week' occurs eight times in the New Testament:

- five times as *μίαν σαββάτων* in connection with Christ's resurrection.¹⁰⁵
- one time as *πρώτη σαββάτου* in Mark's long ending; also, in connection with Christ's resurrection (Mark. 16:9).
- one time in Acts 20:7. Verse 6 details the season: "after unleavened *bread*, and came to them in five days at Troas, where we abstained seven days."¹⁰⁶
- one time in 1 Cor. 16:2 as part of the collection instruction.

In six out of seven instances, *μίαν σαββάτων*¹⁰⁷ undeniably refers to events that took place on or just after Wave Sheaf Offering (≈ Easter Sunday) and thus within the Omer Period. There are no textual reasons why 1 Cor. 16:2 could not also refer to the same period.

Other references to "the Sabbaths"

A reference to a cycle of seven numbered sabbaths (Omer period) is the *ἐν σαββάτῳ δευτεροπρώτῳ* in Luke 6:1.¹⁰⁸ In Nestle-Aland 28,¹⁰⁹ *δευτεροπρώτῳ* is omitted, as Bruce M. Metzger classifies this a *vox nulla*, an accidental blunder by the copyist.¹¹⁰ Hans Klein argues, based on the textual structure, that Luke's writer certainly gave this Sabbath a serial number.¹¹¹ The meaning of *δευτεροπρώτῳ* was obscured early on, as evidenced by the mysterious words of Gregory of Nazianzus quoted by Jerome.¹¹² A precise designation of the Sabbath in Luke 6:1-5 would be textually relevant because of the prohibition against eating fresh ears of corn before the day of the Wave Sheaf Offering.¹¹³ Given the edibility of the ears, this Sabbath should

¹⁰⁴ William Kay, *Commentary on Corinthians I,II* (London: Macmillan and Co, 1887), 84.

¹⁰⁵ Matt. 28:1; Mark 16:2; Luke 24:1; John 10:1&19. The events described in the last verse took place a few days later.

¹⁰⁶ Dating with certainty is difficult. First, Unleavened Bread lasts according to Lev. 23:6 seven days while Luke. 22:1 Equates Unleavened Bread with Passover (only 1 day). Second, textual variants of verse 6 exist: *ἀπὸ ἡμερῶν πέντε* (B⁷⁴ N E 33) instead of *ἄχρι ἡμερῶν πέντε*. Either way, it is certain that these events took place between Pesach and the Feast of Weeks.

¹⁰⁷ Mark 16:9 is omitted here since the Greek form is distinct (*πρώτη σαββάτου*).

¹⁰⁸ In MSS A, C, D, K, N, Θ, etc.; *δευτεροπρώτῳ* missing from MSS P4, B, L, W, etc.

¹⁰⁹ Aland, Barbara et al. (ed.), *Novum Testamentum Graece*, 28th Revised Edition (Stuttgart: Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 2012).

¹¹⁰ B.M. Metzger, *A Textual Commentary on the Greek New Testament*, 2nd edition (Stuttgart: Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 1994), 116.

¹¹¹ Hans Klein, "Miscelle Am ersten Sabbat Eine Konjektur zu Lk 6,1" in *Zeitschrift für die Neutestamentliche Wissenschaft und die Kunde der Älteren Kirche*, Berlin Vol. 87, Iss. 3, (Jan. 1, 1996): 290 -293. <https://doi.org/10.1515/zntw.1996.87.3-4.290>.

¹¹² St. Jerome, "Epistolae 52.8.2" in Perseus Digital Library, "Scaife Viewer | Epistolae," visited 27 December 2021, <https://scaife.perseus.org/reader/urn:cts:latinLit:stoa0162.stoa004.opp-lat1:52.8.2>.

¹¹³ Lev. 23:14.

be close in date to the day of the Wave Sheaf Offering.¹¹⁴ Understood as a 'word for word' translation, by which this Sabbath falls within the Omer Period, yields sensible results, as shown by Luke 6:1 (and its accompanying comments) in the Dutch *Herziene Statenvertaling*:

1 And ^ait came to pass on the second sabbath after the Passover,* that he went through the fields of corn; and his disciples plucked ears of corn, and rubbed them with their hands, and did eat them.

a Deut. 23:25; Matt. 12:1; Mark. 2:23

* The second Sabbath after Passover - Literally: the second-first sabbath.¹¹⁵

As second example which also has a cycle of Sabbaths will be taken from Patristics, by citing the *Stromata*¹¹⁶ of Clemens Alexandrinus (150–215). This passage is polemical in nature and directed against those Jews who do not believe in Jesus. Most likely, his mention of “the sabbath which is called first”¹¹⁷ refers to Easter Sunday, which in the early Church still coincided with the (day of the) Wave Sheaf Offering. Likewise, this may apply to the text of Matt. 28:1: Ὁψὲ δὲ σαββάτων τῆ ἐπιφωσκούσῃ εἰς μίαν σαββάτων. Young's Literal Translation translates this as “And on the eve of the sabbaths, at the dawn, toward the first of the sabbaths.”¹¹⁸

Grammatical analysis

The blank line between chapters 15 and 16

The caesura between 1 Cor. 15:58 and 16:1, presented as a blank line, is assumed primarily because of the *περὶ δὲ* in 1 Cor. 16:1.¹¹⁹ Each *περὶ δὲ* (with a genitive object) presumably indicates the start of an answer by which Paul would point-by-point and sequentially answer written questions he previously received. Consequently, this would always herald a separate topic. The text part from 1 Cor. 7:1 undoubtedly forms an answer to earlier written communication, but this is specifically apparent from the phrase *περὶ δὲ ὧν ἐγράψατε*. However, Paul's argumentation is not interrupted by answering this written question. On the contrary, the answer from 1 Cor. 7:1 is a practical elaboration of the premise given

¹¹⁴ Even so in the method mentioned by Epiphanius whereby this Sabbath falls after Wave Sheaf Offering and within the Omer Period. St. Epiphanius, “Panarion I; 30; 32.6” in *The Panarion of Epiphanius of Salamis Book I (Sects 1-46)*, second edition, trans. Frank Williams (Leiden: Brill, 2009), 161-162.

¹¹⁵ My own translation from the Dutch original: “1 En ^ahet gebeurde op de tweede sabbat na het Paasfeest* dat Hij door de korenvelden ging; en Zijn discipelen plukten aren, wreven die met de handen stuk en aten ze op. ^a Deut. 23:25; Mat. 12:1; Mark. 2:23 * de tweede sabbat na het Paasfeest - Letterlijk: de tweede-eerste sabbat” in *Bijbel Herziene Statenvertaling* (Heerenveen: Jongbloed, 2012), 1623.

¹¹⁶ Clemens Alexandrinus, “Stromatum Liber 6, Caput 5,23” in *PG, tomus IX, tomus secundus*, ed. J.-P. Migne (Parisina: J.-P. Migne, 1857), col. 261.

¹¹⁷ The *σάββατον λεγόμενον πρῶτον* then refers to the first of the seven sabbaths between Wave Sheaf Offering and the Feast of Weeks.

¹¹⁸ Robert Young (trans.), *Young's Literal Translation* (Bellingham: Logos Bible Software, 1997), electronic, without pagenumbers.

¹¹⁹ Schrage follows the consensus opinion here: Mit dem seit 7,1 üblichen *περὶ* nennt V1a den neuen Gegenstand (...). In: Schrage, *Corinther VII/4*, 424.

before it: "Glory therefore God in your body and in your spirit, which are God's" (1 Cor. 6:20). The *περὶ δὲ* in 1 Cor. 12:1 does mark a caesura, but that is on account of the preceding concluding statement, "About the other things I will give instructions when I come." (1 Cor. 11:34^b, NRSV).

In an extensive study of the function of *περὶ δὲ* in Greek texts inside and outside the Bible, Margaret M. Mitchell concludes:

(...) granting that the repetition of the formula *περὶ δὲ* tells us something about the composition of 1 Corinthians, what and how much information can it tell us? (...) What we can say definitely is that each of the topics Paul introduces with the formula *περὶ δὲ* (virgins, idol meat, spiritual people/things, the collection and Apollos) is readily known to both the Corinthians and Paul from *some element of their shared experience*.¹²⁰

Such mutual familiarity (with regards to the subject of 1 Cor. 16:1-5) is confirmed by use of the definite article for both the collection (*τῆς λογιᾶς*) and its beneficiaries (*τοὺς ἀγίους*). Obvious textual elements that, in combination with the *περὶ δὲ*, mandate a caesura between 1 Cor. 15:58 and 16:1 are absent.

Etymology

There is no etymological reason why *μίαν σαββάτων* could not be understood as 'one of the sabbaths' within the Omer period. In a lecture on the etymology of *שַׁבָּת*, Prof. dr. Francois de Blois states:

The most common Greek word for 'week' is *ἑβδομάς*, a classical word for 'group of seven'. But occasionally the 'week' is called *σάββατον*. This is clearly the case in Luke 18:12, the story of the pious tax collector and the hypocritical Pharesee (sic), where the latter says that he fasts *δὶς τοῦ σαββάτου*, which must mean 'twice a week', not 'twice on the Sabbath'. The names of the week days from Sunday to Thursday are formed from the cardinal or (more commonly) ordinal numbers plus the genitive *σαββάτων*, thus, for example, in Matt. 28:1 *μία σαββάτων* 'Sunday', which can be analyzed as '(day) one of the week', though I suppose it could also be understood to mean '(day) one of the (cycle of) Sabbaths'.¹²¹

Note that the formulation '(day) one of the (cycle of) Sabbaths' could be considered an exact reference to the day of the Wave Sheaf Offering.

An enigmatic idiom

The current translation of *κατὰ μίαν σαββάτων* with 'every first day of the week' is unmistakably far removed from its source idiom. The justification for this translation is based on the following assumptions:¹²²

1. The ordinal number *μίαν* is read as a cardinal number.¹²³

¹²⁰ Margaret M. Mitchell, "Concerning *περὶ δὲ* in 1 Corinthians" in *Novum Testamentum*, 31(3) (1989), 233. <https://doi.org/10.1163/156853689x00225>. Emphasis in original.

¹²¹ UCL, "The Etymology of 'Sabbath'", accessed 10 May 2021, <https://blogs.ucl.ac.uk/calendars-ancient-medieval-project/2015/07/15/the-etymology-of-sabbath/>.

¹²² Given the outcome of sub-question 1 (i.e. the similarity of idiom in target languages before 1560), these assumptions should hold equally across all target languages shown in Appendix 1.

¹²³ Change on the original (Dutch) text of the thesis: interchanged ordinal and cardinal (correction).

2. The noun *ἡμέρα* is assumed to be elliptically present.
3. The plural form *σαββάτων* is interchangeable with the singular form.

The following arguments can be advanced to reconsider these three assumptions:

1. In Mark. 14:12 a cardinal number is used to designate the first day of a festival week. In Jub. 3:1 a cardinal number is used in combination with *ἐβδομάς* to designate the first day of a regular week: *τῆ πρώτῃ ἡμέρᾳ ἐβδομάδος, (...)*. The belief that an ordinal number can be read as a cardinal number goes back (probably) to Theophylactus, defending this on the basis of Gen. 1:5. However, the context does not constitute an imperative to understand *ⲧⲏⲣⲏ ⲟⲩ*,¹²⁴ anyway other than 'day one'.¹²⁵ John Lightfoot (1602-1675)¹²⁶ believed that he could further substantiate Theophylactus' argument with Talmudic designation of weekdays.¹²⁷ However, this is anachronistic.
2. Within the NT the noun *ἡμέρα* is present several times to indicate a specific (holiday) weekday: Mark 14:12: *Καὶ τῆ πρώτῃ ἡμέρᾳ τῶν ἀζύμων*; Acts 20:6: *μετὰ τὰς ἡμέρας τῶν ἀζύμων*. Note the actual presence of *ἡμέρα* just prior the supposedly elliptical *ἡμέρα* in verse 7.

If the feminine *μίαν* implies an elliptical feminine *ἡμέρα*,¹²⁸ this should be, depending on (assumed) scope of *μίαν*, either in the dative or accusative case. The LXX contains both forms (e.g. Lev. 24:8: *μνήσθητι τὴν ἡμέραν τῶν σαββάτων* and Ex. 20:8: *τῆ ἡμέρα τῶν σαββάτων*) both referring to the Sabbath as a specific day. Merely adding *ἡμέρα* is not enough to justify the reading 'first day of the week'. This requires both insertion of *τῶν* and the understanding of *σαββάτων* as 'week'.

3. The Greek NT cannot give a definite answer here because interpretation of the context plays a major role. As discussed earlier, Chrysostom certainly did see a distinction between the singular and plural form.¹²⁹

Earlier it turned out that a literal understanding as 'every one of the sabbaths' yielded a sensible result. These grammatical arguments show that a literal understanding is possible and, since it does not require grammatical artifices, it is even more plausible.

¹²⁴ LXX: *ἡμέρα μία*.

¹²⁵ Compare the Dutch idiomatic construction: 'Vanaf dag één ... etc.' (Similarly in English: 'From day one ... etc.').

¹²⁶ John Lightfoot, *A commentary on the New Testament from the Talmud and Hebraica, Matthew-1 Corinthians, Acts-1 Corinthians*, Vol. 4 (Bellingham: Logos Bible Software, 2010), 276.

¹²⁷ E.g. Bab. Talmud, *Baba Qamma* 82A.

¹²⁸ *σαββάτων* is in the neuter case.

¹²⁹ Chrysostom, "Joan. Hom. XI" in *Documenta Catholica Omnia*, "Iohannes Chrysostomus", accessed June 13, 2021, [http://www.documentacatholicaomnia.eu/1004/1003_Ioannes_Chrystostomus_010/0345-0407_Iohannes_Chrysostomus_In_Joannem_MGR.html#\[01807\]](http://www.documentacatholicaomnia.eu/1004/1003_Ioannes_Chrystostomus_010/0345-0407_Iohannes_Chrysostomus_In_Joannem_MGR.html#[01807]).

Sabbath as week

One common opinion is that *σάββατον* can also take on the meaning 'week' in addition to Sabbath, primarily because of the resurrection verses. However, the 20 occurrences of forms of *ἐβδομάδος* within the LXX demonstrate familiarity with that specific word. Lev. 23:15 uses both *σαββάτων* and *ἐβδομάδας* in connection with the Wave Sheaf Offering. Partly triggered by this verse, the Jesuit E. Vogt stated that *שַׁבָּת* can never mean 'week' in the Old Testament.¹³⁰ It was the calendar controversy surrounding the dating of the day of the Wave Sheaf Offering that gave rise to the idea that *שַׁבָּת* could also mean 'week':

Thus, the Pharisees had no choice but to interpret the word "Sabbath" in verses 15b-16 in a different sense, namely as 'week.'¹³¹

Another argument suggesting why *σάββατον* could also mean 'week' is based on the phrase *δὲς τοῦ σαββάτου* found in Luk. 18:12. This is a fictional Pharisee's verbal statement encapsulated within a parable. Extrapolating from Vogt's conclusions, while acknowledging the speaker is a Pharisee, the word *σαββάτου* indeed would mean 'week' here but does not elsewhere. Additionally, *δὲς* can also be used hyperbolically, in an analogous manner as *δὲς ἀποθάνων* in Jude 12.¹³² From these arguments, Luke 18:12 should be understood as caricature rather than being *verbatim*.

interpretation of the *κατὰ*

The preposition *κατὰ*, as present in 1 Cor. 16:2, affects the meaning of *μίαν σαββάτων* in a distributive way, creating a repeating pattern. However, this does not necessarily need to refer to a specific weekday, as de Lacey points out:

Unless *κατὰ μίαν σαββάτου* means simply 'once a week,' with the day then unspecified.¹³³

The combination *κατὰ μίαν* can also be understood in a different manner. In Thucydides *Hist.* 2.83.5 *κατὰ μίαν* is used to indicate that ships are placed 'in a single line': one ship after another.¹³⁴ By analogy with this, *κατὰ μίαν σαββάτων* could be translated as 'during each one of the sabbaths'.

Conclusion of part 3

This section first showed that a literal understanding of *κατὰ μίαν σαββάτων* as 'during each one of the Sabbaths' yields an exegesis that harmonizes with the

¹³⁰ Vogt, E., "Hat 'Šabbāt' im AT den Sinn von 'Woche'?" in *Biblica* 40 (1959), 1008-10. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/42640734>. The provided text is my own translation of the German original: So blieb den Pharisäern nichts anderes übrig, als das Wort "Sabbat" in Vv. 15b16- in einem anderen Sinn aufzufassen, nämlich als 'Woche'.

¹³¹ Ibid., 1009.

¹³² The *δὲς* does not say the tree died twice, but instead it emphasizes that it died completely.

¹³³ Lacey, Douglas, R. de, "The Sabbath/Sunday Question and the Law in the Pauline Corpus" in D. A. Carson (ed.), *From Sabbath to Lord's Day: A Biblical, Historical, and Theological Investigation* (Eugene: Wipf & Stock, 1999), 195.

¹³⁴ E.C. Marchant, *Commentary on Thucydides Book 2* (Medford: MacMillan & Company, 1891), 225.

immediate context, the entire Corinthian letter, and the LXX. Subsequently, it turned out that this translation is certainly permissible on grammatical grounds. In contrast, translating it as 'every first day of the week' requires multiple grammatical assumptions and a 'cutting out' of the 'gathering paragraph' from its textual context. Moreover, if there had been consensus in the early centuries that *μῖαν σαββάτων* actually meant 'first day of the week' based upon grammatical grounds, it is puzzling that this was not echoed in early Latin translations. An early translator such as Jerome, who was capable to study the Tanakh in its original language, adopted 'Jewish-sounding' idiom into the Vulgate despite the availability of alternative and unambiguous Latin idiom.

This section also confirms that the change in form to 'first day of the week' was by no means trivial. Despite one and a half millenniums of stability in form, a shift in conceptual content did take place during that period. The prologue showed a similar shift in the notion of 'the day of the Lord'. This shift was initially theologically based, with grammatical arguments only included at a later time. This section showed similar patterns regarding *μῖαν σαββάτων*.

FINAL CONCLUSION

The central research question involved finding the cause of the translation change in 1 Cor. 16:2. The research into the textual source material as part of sub-question 1 facilitated a targeted historical follow-up research. This research made it clear that the context of the change in form was driven by the understanding of *μῖαν σαββάτων* at that time. The research result of sub-question 3 showed that, taking the Tanakh as frame of reference, a valid exegesis based on a concordant reading is certainly possible. This implies a historical shift in the understanding of this idiom, which eventually led to the observed shape change. The central research question about causation, therefore, needs to be answered on two levels: form and (assumed) conceptual content.

Regarding the form, which is visible on the text surface, the answer was relatively simple. Part 2 suggests that the cause of the change in form lay in the desire to harmonize the text with both *praxis* and the hermeneutic understanding of that time. The hermeneutical bandwidth to interpret this passage in a way other than based on a strictly literal reading had already been created by a theologically motivated broadening of the linguistic field of the Latin *sabbati*. The fact that the change of form did not take place earlier is reasonably explicable because the *depositum fidei* for the Catholic Church is contained in both Tradition and Sacred Scripture.¹³⁵ The change of form, on the other hand, was initiated in 1560 from a community based on *sola scriptura* operating within the strongly religiously polarized era of the 16th century.

Regarding the conceptual content, in which a visible idiom represents an abstract concept, answering the central research question is more complex. Sub-study 3 showed that Greek idiom was available to refer unambiguously to Sunday. It is therefore plausible that with his choice of *μῖαν σαββάτων* Paul advocated such concordant understanding. The loss of this way of understanding is the main cause of the later shape change. A shifted understanding of *μῖαν σαββάτων*, from Wave Sheaf Offering (≈ Easter Sunday) to (every) Sunday, forms the intermediate link. The study of the concept of 'day of the Lord' showed traces of a similar shift in understanding. As two interrelated concepts, the conceptual shift of 'day of the Lord' might have been instrumental for a conceptual shift of *μῖαν σαββάτων*.

There is consensus that the Church, although initially started as (almost completely) Jewish, had become increasingly detached from its Jewish roots. The Tanakh acted increasingly apologetically towards Judaism and less and less as part of the hermeneutical key to interpreting the New Testament. Replacing the Biblical festivals with ecclesiastical ones further diminished understanding of these Biblical festivals and also substituted the frame of reference. Because *μῖαν σαββάτων* mainly occurs in the 'resurrection verses', a reinterpretation as if it points to (Easter) Sunday was understandable. This seemed even more legit since this

¹³⁵ CCC 84.

shift produced no obvious incompatibility with the Gospel text because Wave Sheaf Offering (\approx Easter Sunday) always falls on a Yom Rishon (\approx Sunday).

Practical intuitions

The Church considers Christ's resurrection to be the central truth of the early Christian community.¹³⁶ However, Easter also celebrates Christ's glorious appearance before the Father, which was only possible because of His resurrection. The catechism, therefore, refers to St. Jerome: "The day of the Lord, the day of the resurrection, the day of the Christians, is our day. That is why it is called the day of the Lord: on that day the Lord ascended victorious to the Father."¹³⁷

A rediscovery of Wave Sheaf Offering as an antetype of Easter Sunday can deepen our understanding of the Easter mystery. During Wave Sheaf Offering, Christ presented himself before the Father as the firstfruits from the dead, as a perfect sacrifice in atonement for the people.¹³⁸ Precisely because of this, Christ received the crown of His passion: a heavenly Kingship and Priesthood. This intensifies Easter Sunday. And a proper understanding of this timing may even shed light on the mysterious *noli me tangere*.¹³⁹

Regarding 1 Cor. 16:2 an extra element can be added because a literal and contextual understanding restores the *nexus* between the collection paragraph and the Paschal mystery. The firstfruits of believers effect a symbolic union with Christ's firstfruits,¹⁴⁰ which both includes and transcends 'distributing gifts to the needy.' The exhortation in 1 Cor. 15:58 calls for "work of the Lord." The collection is a concretization of this, giving substance to the Ecumene. The Corinthian firstfruits, however, not only cement their connection with Jerusalem, but also establish a cultic identification with Christ and His firstfruits. This opens an eschatological perspective because in Christ's firstfruits is the guarantee of an eternal reward. It is on this account that a 'work of the Lord' is never in vain ἐν κυρίῳ.¹⁴¹

Closing reflection

In the exact sciences, unlike in hermeneutics, reproducible experiments are possible, allowing for hypotheses to be validated or falsified, and achieving a high degree of certainty. While the author and addressees were not available as witnesses for this research, the available historical Bibles provided evidence of a remarkable translation change. This thesis argues that the usual 'word for word' translation, common until 1560, yields a consistent and coherent exegesis. Only further research can establish whether the views presented in this thesis, the *communis opinio*, or a completely different one, comes closest to the original interpretation.

¹³⁶ CCC 638.

¹³⁷ CCC 1166.

¹³⁸ Lev. 23:11.

¹³⁹ John 20:17 (Vulgate).

¹⁴⁰ CCC 1351.

¹⁴¹ 1 Cor. 15:58.

Chapter 16 of First Corinthians has, according to Thiselton, attracted considerably less controversy and debate than most previous chapters, resulting in about 40 times more monographs and studies on chapter 15 than on chapter 16.¹⁴² Because of the universal importance of money, the low academic attention to the collection section is remarkable. Considering Jesus' statement "Where your treasure is, there is your hart,"¹⁴³ chapter 16 can be considered as *proof of the pudding* for chapter 15. It turns out that there is still a large field of research lying unexplored here.

¹⁴² Thiselton, AC, *The First Epistle to the Corinthians: a commentary on the Greek text* (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 2000), 1314–1315.

¹⁴³ Matt. 6:21 .

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Wilson, Benjamin (trans.). *The Emphatic Diaglott containing the Original Greek tekst of what is commonly styled the New Testament (according to the recension of J.J. Griesbach) with an interlineary word for word English translation; a new emphatic version, based on the interlineary translation, on the renderings of eminent critics, and on the various readings of the Vatican manuscript no. 1209 in the Vatican Library; together with illustrative and explanatory foot notes, and a copious selection of references; to the whole of which is added a valuable alphabetical appendix.* New York: Wowler & Wells Co. 1864. <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t6543090j>.

Wycliffe, John (trans.). *The Holy Bible, containing the Old and New Testaments, with the Apocryphal Books: Early Version, Vol. I–IV.* Redacted by J. Forshall and F. Madden. Oxford: University Press, 1850.

Young, Robert (trans.). *Young's Literal Translation.* Bellingham, WA: Logos Bible Software, 1997.

APPENDIX 1: HISTORICAL TRANSLATIONS

This appendix holds the most important results of the research in response to sub-question 1: “How is 1 Cor. 16:2 translated into different ancient Bibles?”. A table records how the idiom *κατὰ μίαν σαββάτων* is reflected in a large number of historical Bibles. The primary aim was to determine, with a high degree of certainty, the time and place of the observed translation change. To achieve this high degree of certainty, this study mainly used primary source documents which, within the limitations of available fonts, are reproduced in their original spelling. It should be noted that within the time-period and region studied, the various languages had not yet been formalized or distinguished from one another. Illegible or missing text portions are written down by square brackets.

To present the research results clearly and verifiably, an extensive footnote system has been used that includes references to bibliographical data. Due to the nature of the source documents, which include handwritten manuscripts and very old editions that lack bibliographical detail, it is impossible to include a complete and accurate reference for all sources.

In addition to references to the Bible edition as a source document, a separate footnote has also been included with, where possible, a direct hyperlink to a photographic image of the quoted text. If a direct hyperlink proved technically impossible, further instructions were given (such as a reference to a page number within a PDF). The table occasionally has footnotes with additional information, consisting of one or two elements from the following two distinct categories:

- A literal rendering of a commentary as present in the Bible translation, introduced by 'Comment:'.
- Additional notes of various kinds, such as information regarding certain old words or inflections, introduced by 'Note:'.

To limit the size of the footnotes somewhat, titles of web pages or websites have been slightly shortened where appropriate. If the rendered page did not contain any meaningful content or if the <title> tag was missing in the HTML source code, a meaningful title is displayed in the footnotes based on the pages content.

Year/period	Resource name	1 Cor. 16,2 ^a (text)	Facs.
ca. 400	Augustinus (patristische aanhaling in: De Opere Monachorum) ¹⁴⁵	secundum unam sabbati	146
450-500 ¹⁴⁷	Codex Claromontanus (VL 75) ¹⁴⁸	per unam sabbati	149
9 ^e eeuw ¹⁵⁰	Codex Sang. 75 ¹⁵¹	p[er] unam sabbati	152
9 ^e eeuw ¹⁵³	Codex Sangermanensis primus (VL 7) ¹⁵⁴	per una(m) sabbati	155
9 ^e eeuw ¹⁵⁶	Codex Augiensis (VL 78) ¹⁵⁷	per unam sabbati	158
9 ^e eeuw ¹⁵⁹	Codex Boernerianus (VL 77) ¹⁶⁰	[?] una(m) sabbati	161

¹⁴⁵ *Patrologiæ cursus completus, series latina, tomus XL, tomus sextus*, edited by J.-P. Migne (Parisina: J.-P. Migne, 1865).

¹⁴⁶ Augustinus, “De Opere Monachorum, Caput XXIV, 31” in *ibid.*, col. 571.

¹⁴⁷ Note: dating ‘Seconde moitié du Ve siècle.’ Source: Bibliothèque nationale de France, “Consultation”, visited 27 December 2021, <https://archivesetmanuscrits.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/cc21107b>.

¹⁴⁸ *Codex Claromontanus (VL 75)*. Paris: Bibliothèque nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, MS gr. 107AB, Saec. V. <https://n2t.net/ark:/12148/cc21107b>.

¹⁴⁹ Bibliothèque nationale de France, “Saint Paul, Épîtres, texte grec et latin | Gallica”, visited 27 December 2021, <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/btv1b84683111/f347.item>.

¹⁵⁰ Note: according to source: e-codices, “e-codices – Virtual Manuscript Library of Switzerland”, visited 27 December 2021, <https://www.e-codices.ch/en/list/one/csg/0075>.

¹⁵¹ *Codex Biblia latina Vet. et Novi Testamenti*. St. Gallen: Stiftsbibliothek, MS lat. Sang. 75, Saec. IX. <http://doi.org/10.5076/e-codices-csg-0075>.

¹⁵² e-codices, “e-codices – Virtual Manuscript Library of Switzerland”, visited 27 December 2021, <https://www.e-codices.ch/en/csg/0075/810>.

¹⁵³ Note: according the following source: Bibliothèque nationale de France, “Consultation”, visited 27 December 2021, <https://archivesetmanuscrits.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/cc73086c>.

¹⁵⁴ *Codex Proverbes et différents livres de la Bible, version italique*. Paris: Bibliothèque nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, MS lat. 11553, Saec. IX. <https://n2t.net/ark:/12148/btv1b9065958t>.

¹⁵⁵ Bibliothèque Nationale De France, “Proverbes et différents livres de la Bible, version italique”, visited 1 October 2021, <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/btv1b9065958t/f342.item.zoom>.

¹⁵⁶ Barbara Aland et al. (ed.), *Novum Testamentum Graece*, 28th Revised Edition (Stuttgart, Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 2012), 817.

¹⁵⁷ *Codex Augiensis (VL 78)*. Cambridge: Cambridge University, Trinity College, MS B.XVII.1, Saec. IX. https://manuscripts.csntm.org/manuscript/View/GA_010.

¹⁵⁸ The Center for the Study of New Testament Manuscripts, “Manuscript GA 010”, visited 1 October 2021, https://manuscripts.csntm.org/manuscript/Group/GA_010?OSIS=1Cor.16.2.

¹⁵⁹ Barbara Aland et al. (ed.), *Novum Testamentum Graece*, 28th Revised Edition (Stuttgart, Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 2012), 817.

¹⁶⁰ *Codex Boernerianus (VL 77)*. Dresden: Sächsische Landesbibliothek, MS lat. A.145b, Saec. IX. https://manuscripts.csntm.org/manuscript/View/GA_012.

¹⁶¹ Universität Münster - Institut für Neutestamentliche textforschung, “CrossWire Community - Papyri Transcription and Markup”, visited 27 December 2021, <http://ntvnr.uni-muenster.de/community/modules/papyri/?site=VMR&image=20012/1020/10>.

9 ^e eeuw ¹⁶²	Codex Ardmachanus (VL 61) ¹⁶³	p[er] unam sabbati	164
11/12 ^e eeuw	Codex Greek–Latin diglot (GA 620) ¹⁶⁵	p[er] una[m] sabati	166
1200-1300 ¹⁶⁷	Codex Gigas (VL 51, The Devil's Bible) ¹⁶⁸	p[er] una[m] sabbati	169
1350 ¹⁷⁰	Augsburger Bibelhandschrift (Cim 47) ¹⁷¹	durch ein gantze wochen	172
ca. 1375	Codex Wernigerodensis (VL 58) ¹⁷³	p(er) una(m)q(uam)q(ue) sabb(a)ti	174
1382-1395 ¹⁷⁵	Wycliffe ¹⁷⁶	ȝe by oon of the woke	177

¹⁶² Barbara Aland et al. (ed.), *Novum Testamentum Graece*, 28th Revised Edition (Stuttgart, Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 2012), 817.

¹⁶³ *Codex Ardmachanus (VL 61)*. Dublin: Trinity College Library, MS lat. 52, Saec. IX. <https://doi.org/10.48495/3j333696h>.

¹⁶⁴ Trinity College Dublin Digital Collections, “Book of Armagh: IE TCD MS 52”, visited 20 December 2021, <https://digitalcollections.tcd.ie/concern/works/3j333696h>, image 252, folio 121r.

¹⁶⁵ *Codex Greek–Latin diglot (GA 620)*. Florence: Biblioteca Medicea Laurenziana, MS gr./lat. Conv. Soppr. 150, Saec. XII (al. XIII). <http://mss.bmlonline.it/Catalogo.aspx?Shelfmark=Conv.Soppr.150>.

¹⁶⁶ Biblioteca Medicea Laurenziana digital repository, “Biblioteca Medicea Laurenziana - Scaffale Digitale”, visited 28 December 2021, <http://mss.bmlonline.it/s.aspx?Id=AWOS3xqdl1A4r7GxMdbJ&c=EPISTOLAE%20CATHOLICAE%20ET%20ALIA#/oro/189>

¹⁶⁷ Barbara Aland et al. (ed.), *Novum Testamentum Graece*, 28th Revised Edition (Stuttgart, Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 2012), 817.

¹⁶⁸ *Codex Gigas (VL 51)*. Stockholm: Kungliga Biblioteket, MS lat. A. 148, Saec. XIII. <https://hdl.loc.gov/loc.wdl/wdl.3042>.

¹⁶⁹ Library of Congress, “Image 559 of Devil's Bible | Library of Congress”, visited 20 December 2021, https://www.loc.gov/resource/gdcwdl.wdl_03042/?sp=559.

¹⁷⁰ Note: Bayern, 1350, 2. Hälfte des 14. Jahrhunderts. Source: Digitale Bibliothek - Münchener DigitalisierungsZentrum, “Neues Testament, Lektionar, Nikodemus-Evangelium - SuStB Augsburg”, visited 10 December 2021, <https://www.digitale-sammlungen.de/en/details/bsb00087191>.

¹⁷¹ *Codex Augsburger Bibelhandschrift, Neues Testament Lektionar, Nikodemus-Evangelium (Cim 47)*. Augsburg: Staats- und Stadtbibliothek, MS gm. 2^o Cod 3, Saec. XIII. <https://n2t.net/urn:nbn:de:bvb:12-bsb00087191-2>.

¹⁷² Digitale Bibliothek - Münchener DigitalisierungsZentrum, “Neues Testament, Lektionar, Nikodemus-Evangelium”, visited 10 December 2021, <https://www.digitale-sammlungen.de/en/view/bsb00087191?page=556>.

¹⁷³ *Codex Wernigerodensis (VL 58)*. Orlando, FL: The Scriptorium, MS lat. VK 799, Saec. XIV. http://www.itseeweb.bham.ac.uk/epistulae/XML/compaul/07_VL58.xml.

¹⁷⁴ Electronic Resources for the Textual Tradition of the Epistles of Paul, “COMPAUL Transcription Display”, visited 1 October 2021, http://www.itseeweb.bham.ac.uk/epistulae/XML/compaul/07_VL58.xml.

¹⁷⁵ Note: Er zijn meerdere versies waarvan sommige niet afkomstig zijn van Wycliffe zelf.

¹⁷⁶ Wycliffe, John (trans.), *The Holy Bible, containing the Old and New Testaments, with the Apocryphal Books: Early Version*, Vol. I–IV, red. J. Forshall & F. Madden (Oxford: University Press, 1850).

¹⁷⁷ HathiTrust Digital Library, “The New Testament in English translated by John Wycliffe”, visited 10 December 2021, <https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=uc1.31158006169311&view=1up&seq=382>.

ca. 1390	Codex Teplensis (Waldenser Bibel) ¹⁷⁸	Durch am[... ..] des samstaz / Samstag ¹⁷⁹	180
ca.1430	Ottheinrich Bibel ¹⁸¹	durch ein gantßein wochen	182
1435	Neues Testament ¹⁸³	durch ein ganz wochen	184
1454-1456	Guttenbergbibel ¹⁸⁵	p(er) una(m) sabbati	186
1466	Mentelin Bibel (MS) ¹⁸⁷	durch ein des sambstag[s?] jeglichen[?] Sambstag ¹⁸⁸	189
1466	Mentelin Bibel (gedruckt) ¹⁹⁰	durch einen des sambstags	191
1470	Eggestein Bibel ¹⁹²	durch einen des sambstags	193

¹⁷⁸ *Codex Teplensis [Di schrift dez newen geczeuges] (Waldenser Bibel)*. Teplá, Česká republika: Klášter premonstrátů Teplá, knihovna, MS gm. B 10, Saec. XIV. http://www.manuscriptorium.com/apps/index.php?direct=record&pid=AIPDIG-KPTK_0B_10_____1693C11-cs#search.

¹⁷⁹ Note: The text is difficult to reconstruct due to erasures and corrections placed in the margin (possibly even in two different handwritings). This indicates that the meaning of the idiom was likely not evident to the translator(s).

¹⁸⁰ National Library of the Czech Republic Manuscriptorium, “default.jpg”, visited 1 October 2021, https://imagines.manuscriptorium.com/loris/AIPDIG-KPTK_0B_10_____1693C11-cs/ID0348P/full/full/0/default.jpg.

¹⁸¹ *Codex Ottheinrichs-Bibel (Cgm 8010)*, Bd. 5. München: Bayerische Staatsbibliothek, MS gm. Cgm 8010/5, Saec. XV. <https://n2t.net/urn:nbn:de:bvb:12-bsb00032720-6>.

¹⁸² Digitale Bibliothek - Münchener DigitalisierungsZentrum, “Ottheinrich-Bibel, Bd. 5: Röm 15,13 - Kol 3,22”, visited 10 December 2021, <https://daten.digital-sammlungen.de/0003/bsb00032720/images/index.html?id=00032720&seite=35>.

¹⁸³ *Codex Neues Testament, Plenar; Nikodemus-Evangelium*. Stuttgart: Württembergische Landesbibliothek, MS gm. bibl. fol. 15, [1435]. <https://n2t.net/urn:nbn:de:bsz:24-digibib-bsz4097549944>.

¹⁸⁴ Württembergische Landesbibliothek, “werkansicht - Neues Testament - Cod.bibl.fol.15”, visited 8 December 2021, https://digital.wlb-stuttgart.de/index.php?id=6&tx_dlf%5Bid%5D=5890&tx_dlf%5Bpage%5D=333.

¹⁸⁵ [*Biblia latina*] (Mainz: Johannes Gutenberg, [ca. 1454]). <https://n2t.net/ark:/12148/cb35951126v>.

¹⁸⁶ Bibliothèque nationale de France, “Bible de Gutenberg : [Biblia latina]. Ex. sur papier - Volume 2”, visited 27 December 2021, <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k9914329/f468.item>.

¹⁸⁷ *Codex Mentelin Bibel*. Freiburg: Universitätsbibliothek Freiburg, MS. 22a, [1466-1471]. <https://n2t.net/urn:nbn:de:bsz:25-digilib-101985>.

¹⁸⁸ Note: The presence of strikethroughs in the text indicates that the translator(s) experienced a certain degree of uncertainty regarding the meaning of the idiom in the source language (in this case, Latin).

¹⁸⁹ Universitätsbibliothek Freiburg, “Bibel [s. I.], [1466-1471] Blatt: 341r”, visited 20 April 2021, <http://dl.ub.uni-freiburg.de/diglit/hs22a/0687>.

¹⁹⁰ [*Biblia: Übers. aus dem Lat. Mit dt. Tituli psalmorum*] ([Straßburg]: [Johannes Mentelin], [voor 27 juni 1466]). <https://n2t.net/urn:nbn:de:bvb:12-bsb00036981-0>.

¹⁹¹ Digitale Bibliothek - Münchener DigitalisierungsZentrum, “[Biblia], [Übers. aus dem Lat. Mit dt. Tituli psalmorum], [Straßburg]”, visited 20 October 2021, http://daten.digital-sammlungen.de/bsb00036981/image_734.

¹⁹² [*Biblia <dt.>*] ([Straßburg]: [Heinrich Eggestein], [Not after 1470]). <http://data.onb.ac.at/rec/AC07662865>.

¹⁹³ Österreichische Nationalbibliothek, “Biblia <dt.> [Straßburg]: [Heinrich Eggestein], 1470. - 2°. - 404 Bl. 2 Sp. 60 Z.”, visited 12 October 2021, https://digital.onb.ac.at/RepViewer/viewer.faces?doc=DTL_1253975&order=1&view=SINGLE.

ca. 1475	Pflanzmann Bibel ¹⁹⁴	durch einen des sambstags	195
ca. 1475/76	Zainer Bible ¹⁹⁶	durch einen des samtstags	197
1476-78	Sensenschmidt Bibel ¹⁹⁸	durch einen des sapstags	199
1477	Sorg Bibel ²⁰⁰	durch ei[n]en des sambstags	201
1481	Biblia Latina ²⁰²	per una sabbati ²⁰³	204
1481	Manerbi Venedig ²⁰⁵	per vno di dla septimana ²⁰⁶	207
1483	Koberger-Bibel ²⁰⁸	durch einen des sabbaths	209

¹⁹⁴ [*Biblia (deutsch)*] ([Augsburg]: [Jodocus Pflanzmann], [ca. 1475]). <https://doi.org/10.3931/e-rara-12274>.

¹⁹⁵ e-rara, the platform for digitized rare books from Swiss institutions, "ZB Zürich / Biblia (deutsch)", visited 13 October 2021, <https://www.e-rara.ch/zuz/content/zoom/3833977>.

¹⁹⁶ [*Biblia: Übersetzt aus dem Lateinischen. Mit deuschem Tituli psalmorum und Register*] (Augsburg: [Günther Zainer], [ca. 1475/76]). <https://n2t.net/urn:nbn:de:bvb:12-bsb00025979-2>.

¹⁹⁷ Digitale Bibliothek - Münchener Digitalisierungszentrum, "[Biblia], Augsburg, [ca. 1475/76]", visited 12 October 2021, http://daten.digitale-sammlungen.de/bsb00025979/image_427.

¹⁹⁸ [*Biblia: übers. aus dem Lat.; mit dt. Tituli psalmorum und Register. T. 1-2, Bd.: 2*] ([Nürnberg]: s.n., [1476/78]). <https://n2t.net/urn:nbn:de:bvb:12-bsb00026112-6>.

¹⁹⁹ Digitale Bibliothek - Münchener Digitalisierungszentrum, "Biblia, übers. aus dem Lat. ; mit dt. Tituli psalmorum und Register. T. 1-2, Bd.: 2, [Nürnberg],", visited 12 October 2021, http://daten.digitale-sammlungen.de/bsb00026112/image_425.

²⁰⁰ [*Biblia: übers. aus dem Lat., mit dt. Tituli psalmorum und Register / 2*] (Augsburg: Anton Sorg, 1477). <https://n2t.net/urn:nbn:de:bvb:12-bsb00025989-8>.

²⁰¹ Digitale Bibliothek - Münchener Digitalisierungszentrum, "Biblia, übers. aus dem Lat., mit dt. Tituli psalmorum und Register, Bd.: 2, Augsburg, (1477.06.20.)", visited 13 October 2021, http://daten.digitale-sammlungen.de/bsb00025989/image_451.

²⁰² [*Biblia: Mit Postilla litteralis von Nicolaus de Lyra, Expositiones prologorum von Guilelmus Brito, Additiones ad Postillam Nicolai de Lyra von Paulus Burgensis und Replica contra Burgensem von Matthias Doering*] (Nuremberge: impensisq[ue] Anthonij kobergers, 1493). <https://n2t.net/urn:nbn:de:bvb:12-bsb00060379-9>.

²⁰³ Note: comment by Nicolaas de Lyra. Comment: Per una sabbati i. prima die hebdomade q vocat sabbatu in pluribus locis scripture VII lu.XVIII Jeinno bis in sabbato.i. in hebdomada, sunit vna accipit [unclear symbol] ptia Gen 1. Faciit e mane ? vespe dies un. Note: this is referring to Gen 1:5: יוֹם אֶחָד.

²⁰⁴ Digitale Bibliothek - Münchener Digitalisierungszentrum, "Nicolaus <de Lyra> / Guilelmus <Brito, Exegeta> / Paulus <Burgensis>: Biblia, Mit Postilla litteralis von Nicolaus de Lyra", visited 10 October 2021, http://daten.digitale-sammlungen.de/bsb00060379/image_402.

²⁰⁵ Nicolò Manerbi (trad.), *Biblia* (Venedig: Bartolomeo Fonte, 1481). <https://n2t.net/urn:nbn:de:bvb:12-bsb00048362-2>.

²⁰⁶ Note: per vno di dla [=della] septimana = for one of the weeks.

²⁰⁷ Digitale Bibliothek - Münchener Digitalisierungszentrum, "Manerbi, Nicolò / Aristeas <Epistolographus> / Fonte, Bartolomeo: Biblia, Venedig, 1481", visited 14 October 2021, http://daten.digitale-sammlungen.de/bsb00048362/image_788.

²⁰⁸ [*Biblia*] (Nürnberg: Anton Koberger, 1483). <https://doi.org/10.11588/diglit.16667>.

²⁰⁹ Universitätsbibliothek Heidelberg - historic literature – digitized, "Biblia, deutsch. — Nürnberg, 17. Februar 1483 [GW 04303]", visited 13 October 2021, <https://digi.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/diglit/ib00632000/1075>.

1484	Bibbia del Malermi ²¹⁰	per vno di della septimana	211
1485	Grüninger Bibel ²¹²	durch einen des sabaths	213
1487	Bibbia Jensoniana ²¹⁴	per ciascuno sabbato ²¹⁵	216
1490 ?	Malermi Bible? ²¹⁷	Uno di dela septimana	218
1490	Schönsperger-Bibel ²¹⁹	durch einen des sabbaths	220
1494	Lübecker Bibel ²²¹	dör enē des Sabbatdaghes	222

²¹⁰ Niccolo Malermi (trad.), *Bibbia Traduction italienne par Niccolo Malermi ...* (Venise: Andrea Paltasichi, 1484). <https://mazarinum.bibliotheque-mazarine.fr/ark:/61562/mz1760>.

²¹¹ Bibliothèque numérique de la Bibliothèque Mazarine, "Bibbia", visited 14 October 2021, <https://mazarinum.bibliotheque-mazarine.fr/viewer/1760/?offset=#page=712>.

²¹² *Biblia Sacra, das ist Die Hielige Schrift de Alten und Neuen Testaments. Anderer Theil* (Straßburg: [Johann Grüninger], 1485). <https://n2t.net/urn:nbn:de:bvb:12-bsb00025992-6>.

²¹³ Digitale Bibliothek - Münchener DigitalisierungsZentrum, "Biblia, übers. aus dem Lat., mit dt. Tituli psalmorum. [1-2], Bd.: 2, Straßburg, (1485.05.02.)", visited 13 October 2021, http://daten.digitale-sammlungen.de/bsb00025992/image_757.

²¹⁴ [Nicolò Malermi (trad.)], "La Bibbia Volgare" in *La Bibbia Volgare, Secondo La Rara Ed. Del i Di Ottobre 1471, Ristampata per Cura Di C. Negroni. 10 Voll.*, volume 10 (Bologna: Presso Romagnoli Dall' Acqua, 1887). Originaly: [*La Bibbia Volgare*] ([Venezia]: [Vindelino da Spira?], 1471). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=P0NbAAAAQAAJ>.

²¹⁵ Note: literally understood as 'for each Sabbath.

²¹⁶ Google Books, "La Bibbia volgare, secondo la rara ed. del i di ottobre 1471 ..., Volume 10", visited 14 October 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=P0NbAAAAQAAJ&pg=PA146>.

²¹⁷ [*Biblia Vvlgare Istoriata*] ([Venice]: [Giovanni Ragazzo], [1490]). <https://digital.bodleian.ox.ac.uk/objects/492fe240-6937-411b-80a5-90bceed299fe>.

²¹⁸ Digital Bodleian (University of Oxford), "Bodleian Library Douce 244", visited 14 October 2021, <https://digital.bodleian.ox.ac.uk/objects/492fe240-6937-411b-80a5-90bceed299fe/surfaces/95cadadc-c21c-43fb-ae3e-5cf8d99c64d9/>.

²¹⁹ *Das ander teyl der Bibel 2: Das Buch Der sprüch - Das buch Der heymlichen offenbarung* (Augsburg: Johann Schönsperger, 1490). <https://n2t.net/urn:nbn:de:bvb:12-bsb00026207-2>.

²²⁰ Digitale Bibliothek - Münchener DigitalisierungsZentrum, "Biblia, übers. aus dem Lat., mit dt. Tituli psalmorum. T. 1-2, Bd.: 2, Augsburg, (1490.11.09.)", visited 13 October 2021, http://daten.digitale-sammlungen.de/bsb00026207/image_838.

²²¹ *De Biblie mit vlitigher achtighe: recht na deme latine in dusesck auerghesettet Mit vorluchtinghe vnde glose: des hochghelerden Postillatoers Nicolai de lyra Vnde anderer velen hillighen doctoren* (Lübeck: Steffen Arndes, 1494). <https://n2t.net/urn:nbn:de:bvb:12-bsb00025548-9>.

²²² Digitale Bibliothek - Münchener DigitalisierungsZentrum, "Biblia, übers. aus dem Lat., mit Glossen nach der Postilla litteralis des Nicolaus de Lyra, Vorrede und Register, Lübeck, 1494.11.19. [BSB-Ink B-495 - GW 4309]", visited 16 October 2021, http://daten.digitale-sammlungen.de/bsb00025548/image_906.

1495	La Bible Mangeur ²²³	par vng jour de la sepmaine ²²⁴	225
1507	Otmar Bibel ²²⁶	durch eine des sabbaths	227
1516	Novum Instrumentum omne ²²⁸	in una(m) sabbato	229
1518	Rynman Bibel ²³⁰	durch einen des sabbaths	231
1519	Novum Testamentum Omne ^{232,233}	In una sabbatorum	234
1522	Halberstädter Bibel ²³⁵	dorch eyne des sabbatdages	236

²²³ [Pierre le Mangeur (trad.)], *Le second volume dela bible en francois historiee* (s.l.: [Antoine Vérard], [1495]). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=vo1PnouVTQEC>.

²²⁴ Note: To be understood as 'on a day of the week'. Justification: The word 'vng' also appears in 1 Cor. 15:52. The phrase 'ce sera en vng moment' [v=u] (it will be in a moment) is a translation of the Latin 'in ictu couli' (in the blink of an eye). 'Ung' is a declension of 'un' according to Dictionnaire Étymologique de l'Ancien Français, "DEAF électronique", visited 13 October 2021, <https://deaf-server.adw.uni-heidelberg.de/lemme/un#un>.

²²⁵ Google Books, "La Bible historiée", visited 13 October 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=vo1PnouVTQEC&pg=PP562>.

²²⁶ *Bibel teutsch der ander tayl* (s.l.: Hans Otmar, 1507). <https://books.google.de/books?id=pL9IAAAAcAAJ>.

²²⁷ Google Books, "Bibel teutsch der ander tayl", visited 13 October 2021, <https://books.google.de/books?id=pL9IAAAAcAAJ&pg=PP664>.

²²⁸ Desiderius Erasmus (trans.), *Novum Instrumentum omne: diligenter ab Erasmo Roterodamo recognitum ... una cum Annotationibus* (Basileæ: Johannes Froben, 1516). <https://doi.org/10.3931/e-rara-2849>.

²²⁹ e-rara, the platform for digitized rare books from Swiss institutions, "UB Basel / Novum Instrumentum", visited 1 October 2021, https://www.e-rara.ch/bau_1/content/zoom/895965.

²³⁰ *Bibel teütsch der ander tail* ([Augsburg]: [Rynman], [1518]). <https://books.google.de/books?id=GO1oAAAAcAAJ>.

²³¹ Google Books, "Bibel teütsch der ... tail: 2", visited 13 October 2021, <https://books.google.de/books?id=GO1oAAAAcAAJ&pg=PP664>.

²³² Desiderius Erasmus (trans.), *Novum Testamentum Omne, multo quàm antehac diligentius ab Erasmo Roterodamo recognitu, emedatum ac translatum ...* (Basileæ: Ioannis Frobenii, 1519). <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t1bk2bm6w>.

²³³ Note: On the title page, Erasmus provides references to many earlier commentators: emédationem & interpretationé, præcipue Origenis, Athanafij, Nazianzeni, Chryloftomí, Cyrilli; Theophylacti, Hieronymí, Cypriani, Ambrosij, Hilarij, Auguftini. Source: Internet Archive, "Novum Testamentum omne, multo quàm antehac diligentius ab Erasmo Roterodamo...", visited 20 December 2021, <https://archive.org/details/novumtestamentum00eras/page/n3/mode/2up>.

²³⁴ Internet Archive, "Novum Testamentum omne, multo quàm antehac diligentius ab Erasmo Roterodamo...", visited 19 October 2021, <https://archive.org/details/novumtestamentum00eras/page/378/mode/2up>.

²³⁵ *Biblia dudesch dat ander deell* (Halberstadt: [Lorenz Stuchs], 1522). <https://n2t.net/urn:nbn:de:bvb:12-bsb00084031-5>.

²³⁶ Digitale Bibliothek - Münchener DigitalisierungsZentrum, "Biblia dudesch dat ... deell, Bd.: 2, Halberstad, (1522) [VD16 B 2839]", visited 13 October 2021, http://daten.digitalisierungs-zentrum.de/bsb00084031/image_452.

1522	Novum Testamentum omne ²³⁷	in una sabbaton	238
1522	Luthers Septembertestament ²³⁹	auff iah der Sabbather eynen	240
1524	Luther NT (Zurich) ²⁴¹	auf der Sabather einen	242
1524	Niewe Testame[n]t (Erasmus) ²⁴³	In een va[n]den sabbath	244
1526 ²⁴⁵	Tyndale New Testament ²⁴⁶	In some saboth daye	247
1527	Novum Testamentum (Erasmus) ²⁴⁸	in una(m) sabbatoru(m)	249

²³⁷ Desiderius Erasmus (trans.), *Novum testamentum omne: tertio iam ac diligentius [sic] ab Erasmo Roterodamo recognitum: non solum ad Grecam veritatem: ...* (Basileæ: Pamphili Gengenbachii, 1522). <https://doi.org/10.3931/e-rara-943>.

²³⁸ e-rara, the platform for digitized rare books from Swiss institutions, "UB Basel / Novum testamentum", visited 20 October 2021, https://www.e-rara.ch/bau_1/content/zoom/1153737.

²³⁹ Maarten Luther (übers.), "Septemberbibel" in *Deutsche Drucke älterer Zeit in nachbildungen herausgegeben von Dr. Wilhelm Scherer ...*, I. Luther: Septemberbibel (Berlin: G. Grote'sche Verlagsbuchhandlung, 1883). Originaly: *Das Neue Testament Deutsch von Martin Luther* (Wittenberg: Melchior Lotter, 1522). <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t2h71769q>.

²⁴⁰ Internet Archive, "Das Neue Testament Deutzsch, 1522", visited 13 October 2021, <https://archive.org/details/DasNeueTestamentDeutzsch1522/page/n286/mode/1up>.

²⁴¹ *Das gantz Nüw Testame[n]t recht grüntlich vertütscht: ...* (Zürich: Johannem Hager, 1524). <https://doi.org/10.3931/e-rara-686>.

²⁴² e-rara, the platform for digitized rare books from Swiss institutions, "ZB Zürich / Das gantz Nüw Testament... [529]", visited 13 October 2021, <https://www.e-rara.ch/zuz/content/zoom/191929>.

²⁴³ Desiderius Erasmus (vert.), *Dat niewe Testame[n]t. welc is dat leuende woert Goods, wtghesproken doer onsen salichmaker Iesus Christus ...* (Delft: Cornelis Heynrickz, [1524]). <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t0qr7q63c>.

²⁴⁴ Internet Archive, "Dat Niewe Testame[n]t.(sec.) welc is dat leuende woert Goods, wtghesproken doer onsen salichmaker Iesus Christus", visited 16 October 2021, <https://archive.org/details/ned-kbn-all-00003167-001/page/n516/mode/2up>.

²⁴⁵ Note: according to the source document: "A facsimile of Tyndale's 1526 New Testament with both title pages added to make it a "complete" edition." Source: Internet Archive, "1526 Tyndale New Testament", visited 28 December 2021, <https://archive.org/details/0410Tyndale1526NT/page/n1/mode/2up>.

²⁴⁶ Wiliam Tyndale (trans.), "The Newe Testamente as it was written ..." in *The Newe Testamente* (s.l.: s.n., s.a.). Original title: *The Newe Testamente as it was written ...* ([Worms?]: [Peter Schöffner], [1526]). <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t5m92n13c>.

²⁴⁷ Internet Archive, "1526 Tyndale New Testament", visited 4 October 2021, <https://archive.org/details/0410Tyndale1526NT/page/n237/mode/2up>.

²⁴⁸ Desiderius Erasmus (trans.), *En Novum Testamentum, ex Erasmi Roterodami recognitione, iam quartum damus studiose lector: ...* (Basileæ: Johannes Froben, 1527). <https://doi.org/10.3931/e-rara-2584>.

²⁴⁹ e-rara, the platform for digitized rare books from Swiss institutions, "UB Basel / Ioannes Frobenius candido... [424]", visited 20 October 2021, https://www.e-rara.ch/bau_1/content/zoom/838910.

1527	NT Emster ²⁵⁰	auf der sabather eynen	251
1528	Zurich Latin Bible (Zwinglibibel) ²⁵²	Auf der Sabbathe einen	253
1530	Luther NT Zurich Froshouer ²⁵⁴	Auff der Sabbathen einen	255
1530	Il Nvovo Testamento ²⁵⁶	in uno de sabbati ²⁵⁷	258
1531	Biblia germanice ²⁵⁹	auf der sabbathen einen	260
1531	Vorsterman Bijbel ²⁶¹	een nae den sabothen ²⁶²	263

²⁵⁰ [Hieronymus Emser? (red.)], *Das naw Testament nach lawt der Christliche kirchen bewerte tekst / corrigirt / und wider umb zu recht gebracht* ([Emster?]: [Wolfgang Stöckel], 1527). <https://books.google.de/books?id=6ylJAAAAcAAJ>.

²⁵¹ Google Books, “Das naw Testament”, visited 12 October 2021, <https://books.google.de/books?id=6ylJAAAAcAAJ&pg=RA1-PP12>.

²⁵² [*Neues Testament. Deutsch*] (Zürich: Christoffel Froshauer, 1528). <https://doi.org/10.3931/e-rara-15845>.

²⁵³ e-rara, the platform for digitized rare books from Swiss institutions, “ZB Zürich / [Neues Testament. Deutsch]”, visited 13 October 2021, <https://www.e-rara.ch/zuz/content/zoom/4931539>.

²⁵⁴ Maarten Luther (übers.), *Die gantze Bibel: der ursprüngliche[n] Ebraischenn unnd Griechischenn warheyt nach, auffs aller treüwlichet verteütschet* (Zürich: Christoph Froshauer, 1530). <https://n2t.net/urn:nbn:de:bvb:12-bsb00028058-3>.

²⁵⁵ Digitale Bibliothek - Münchener DigitalisierungsZentrum, “Luther, Martin: Die gantze Bibel”, visited 13 October 2021, http://daten.digitale-sammlungen.de/bsb00028058/image_1084.

²⁵⁶ Antonio Brvcioli (trad.), *Il Nvovo Testamento di Giesu Christo ...* (Venetia: s.n.,1530). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=zL9IAAAAacAAJ>.

²⁵⁷ Note: literally: on one of the Saturdays/Sabbaths. Matt. 28:1 reads: in uno de sabbat.

²⁵⁸ Google Books, “Il nuovo testamento di Giesu Christo ... di greco tradotto ... per Antonio”, visited 13 October 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=zL9IAAAAacAAJ&pg=RA1-PA61-IA1>.

²⁵⁹ *Die gantze Bibel der vrsprünglichen Ebraischen vnd Griechischen Waarheyt nach auffs aller treüwlichet verteütschet*, Band 2 (Zürich: Christoffel Froshauer, 1531). <https://books.google.de/books?id=I8BIAAAAacAAJ>.

²⁶⁰ Google Books, “Die gantze Bibel der vrsprünglichen Ebraischen vnd Griechischen, Band 2”, visited 13 October 2021, <https://books.google.de/books?id=I8BIAAAAacAAJ&hl=de&pg=PR279-IA1>.

²⁶¹ *De Bibel. Tgeheele Oude ende Nieuwe Testament met grooter naersticheyt naden Latijnschen text gecorrigeert, ...* ([Antwerpen]: [Willem Vorsterman], [1528/1531]). <https://www.bijbelsdigitaal.nl/view/?bible=vorst1531>.

²⁶² Note: Most likely to be understood literally as: 'one towards the Sabbaths'. The Old Dutch 'nae' can mean both 'after' (as in 'Hier nae volcht dat Euangelium van Sinte Ioannes', 'Here after follows the Gospel of Saint John') and 'towards'. The latter meaning is most likely, given the multiple uses of 'nae' meaning 'towards' within the same letter (1 Cor. 3:2, 3:10, 10:18, 15:23).

²⁶³ Nederlands-Vlaams Bijbelgenootschap, “Vorstermanbijbel (1528/1531): Totten Corinthen.i”, visited 13 October 2021, <https://www.bijbelsdigitaal.nl/view/?mode=1&bible=vorst1531&page=1093&sub=1-2>.

1534	Dietenberger ²⁶⁴ Bibel ²⁶⁵	Auff der Sabbather eine ²⁶⁶	267
1534	Duitse Bijbel (Zürich, Christoffel Froschouer) ²⁶⁸	auff der Sabbathe einen	269
1534	La Sainte Bible ²⁷⁰	Par vng io(ur) de Sabbat ²⁷¹	272
1534	Luther Bibel, Wittenberg (druk: Hans Lufft) ²⁷³	Auff j[?] der Sabbather einen	274
1535	In Novum Testamentum Annotationes (Erasmus) ²⁷⁵	Per unam sabatti ²⁷⁶	277
1535	Novum Testamentum (Erasmus) ²⁷⁸	in una sabbatorum	279

²⁶⁴ Note: Dr. Johan Dietenberger (*1475, †1537) was a Dominican, Professor of Theology, and Grand Inquisitor in Mainz. His translation served as a Catholic response to Luther, and his Bible was popularly known as the ‘Catholic Bible.’

²⁶⁵ Johan Dietenberger (übers.), *Biblia, beider Allt unnd Newen Testamenten: fleissig, treülich un[d] Christlich, nach alter, inn Christlicher kirchen gehabter Translation, ...* (Meyns: [Quentel], 1534). <https://books.google.de/books?id=UUhbcjYXWEMC>.

²⁶⁶ Note: Translation at Matt. 28:1: (...) am morgen des ersten tag der Sabbatten (...).

²⁶⁷ Google Books, “Biblia, beider Allt unnd Newen Testamenten”, visited 10 December 2021, <https://books.google.de/books?id=UUhbcjYXWEMC&pg=RA2-PP8>.

²⁶⁸ *Bibel Teütsch, der ursprünglichen Hebreischen und Griechischen warheit nach, aufs treüwlichet verdometschet ...* (Zürich: Christoffel Froschouer, 1534). <https://n2t.net/urn:nbn:de:bvb:12-bsb00024266-8>.

²⁶⁹ Digitale Bibliothek - Münchener DigitalisierungsZentrum, “Bibel Teütsch, der ursprünglichen Hebreischen und Griechischen warheit nach, aufs treüwlichet verdometschet”, visited 10 December 2021, http://daten.digitale-sammlungen.de/bsb00024266/image_1118.

²⁷⁰ *La Sainte Bible en francoys, translatée selon la pure et entière traduction de Saint Hierome. derechief conferee et entierement reuisitee selon les plus anciens ...* (Anvers: Martin Lempereur, 1534). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=57QQINcyQqIC>.

²⁷¹ Note: To be understood as ‘on a day of the week’. Justification: The word ‘vng’ also appears in 1 Cor. 15:52. The phrase ‘ce sera en vng moment’ [v=u] (it will be in a moment) is a translation of the Latin ‘in ictu couli’ (in the blink of an eye). ‘Ung’ is a declension of ‘un’ according to Dictionnaire Étymologique de l’Ancien Français, “DEAF électronique”, visited 13 October 2021, <https://deaf-server.adw.uni-heidelberg.de/lemme/un#un>.

²⁷² Google Books, “La Sainte Bible en Francoys translatee”, visited 15 October 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=57QQINcyQqIC&pg=PT204>.

²⁷³ Martin Luther (übers.), *Biblia, das ist, die gantze Heilige Schrift Deudsch. Mart. Luth. Wittemberg. Begnadet mit Kurfürstlicher zu Sachsen freiheit* (Wittenberg: Hans Lufft, 1534). <https://n2t.net/urn:nbn:de:gbv:32-1-10016175488>.

²⁷⁴ Digitale Sammlungen der Herzogin Anna Amalia Bibliothek, “Die Propheten || alle Deudsch.|| D. Mar. Luth.|| ([Bd. 2])”, visited 12 December 2021, <http://haab-digital.klassik-stiftung.de/viewer/image/935052658/839/>.

²⁷⁵ Desiderius Erasmus, *Des Erasmi Roterdami In Novvm Testamentvm Annotationes ...* (Basileæ: Officina Frobiani, 1535). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=X6poAAAACAAJ>.

²⁷⁶ Comment: σαββάτων, id est, Sabbatorum. Theophylactus admonet Vnam, dictam esse pro Primam: significarie autem diem dominicum, in quo confentit Chrylostomus.

²⁷⁷ Google Books, “In Novum Testamentum Annotationes”, visited 10 December 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=X6poAAAACAAJ&pg=PA520>.

²⁷⁸ Desiderius Erasmus (trans.), *Novi Testamenti aeditio postrema, per Des. Erasmus Roterodamum* (Basileæ: Officina Frobiani, 1535). <https://doi.org/10.3931/e-rara-4806>.

²⁷⁹ e-rara, the platform for digitized rare books from Swiss institutions, “UB Basel / Novi Testamenti aeditio... [528]”, visited 20 October 2021, https://www.e-rara.ch/bau_1/content/zoom/1445848.

1536	Duitse Bijbel (Froschouer) ²⁸⁰	auf der sabbathen einen	281
1537	Katholische Eck-Bibel ²⁸²	Auf der sabbath ain	283
1538	La Bibia ²⁸⁴	in vn de sabbati	285
1540	The Great Bible ²⁸⁶	Upon some Saboth daye	287
1542	Liesveltbijbel ²⁸⁸ ,	op der sabbath een	289
1543	Novum Testamentum omne ²⁹⁰	in una sabbattorum	291
1544	Biblia Sacrosancta ²⁹²	Per vnam sabbathi	293

²⁸⁰ *Die gantze Bibel, das ist alle Buecher Allts und Neüws Testaments / den ursprünglichen Spraachen nach auff's aller treüwlichet verteütschet. ...* (Zürich: Christoffel Froschouer, 1540). <https://doi.org/10.3931/e-rara-1703>.

²⁸¹ e-rara, the platform for digitized rare books from Swiss institutions, "ZB Zürich / Die gantze Bibel, das ... [1283", visited 20 December 2021, <https://www.e-rara.ch/zuz/content/zoom/535464>.

²⁸² Johannes Eck (übers.), *Bibel, Alt vnd new Testament/ nach dem Text in der hailigen Kirchen gebraucht/ ...* (Ingolstat: Görg Krapffen, 1537). <https://n2t.net/urn:nbn:de:bvb:12-bsb00104979-2>.

²⁸³ Bavarikon, "Johannes Eck, Bibel", visited 13 October 2021, <https://www.bavarikon.de/object/bav:BSB-HSS-00000BSB00104979?lang=de>, 1189.

²⁸⁴ Marmochino Fiorentino (trad.), *La Bibia Nvovamente Tradotta Dalla Hebraica verita in lingua thoscana* (Vinegia: [Lucantonio Giunti], 1538). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=7-BYAAAACAAJ>.

²⁸⁵ Google Books, "La Bibia Nvovamente Tradotta Dalla Hebraica verita in lingua thoscana", visited 14 October 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=7-BYAAAACAAJ&pg=RA3-PA57-IA1>.

²⁸⁶ *The Byble in Englyihe, that is to saye the contet of al the holy scrypture* (s.l.: Edward Whytchurche, 1540). <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t7kp90k79>.

²⁸⁷ Internet Archive, "Great Bible, 1540", visited 15 October 2021, <https://archive.org/details/GreatBible1540/page/n497/mode/1up>.

²⁸⁸ *Den Bybel met groter neersticheyt ghecorrigeert, ende op dye canten ghesedt den ouderdom der werelt, ...* ([Antwerpen?]: [Liesvelt], [1542]). <https://www.bijbelsdigitaal.nl/view/?mode=1&bible=liesv1542>.

²⁸⁹ Nederlands-Vlaams Bijbelgenootschap, "Liesveltbijbel (1542): Totten Corinthen", visited 14 October 2021, <https://www.bijbelsdigitaal.nl/view/?mode=1&bible=liesv1542&page=783&sub=1-2>.

²⁹⁰ Desiderius Erasmus, *Nouum Testamentum graece & latine / iuxta veterum, cum graecorum, tum latinorum, emendatissima exemplaria accuratissima cura & diligentia D. Erasmi Roterod* (Parisiis: Carola Guillard, 1543). <http://bdh.bne.es/bnearch/detalle/bdh0000069294>.

²⁹¹ Biblioteca Digital Hispánica, "Nouum Testamentum graece & latine", visited 14 October 2021, <http://bdh-rd.bne.es/viewer.vm?id=0000069294&page=286>.

²⁹² *Biblia Sacrosancta Testamenti Veteris & Novi, iuxta vulgatam quam dicunt aeditionem, ...* (Lugduni: Hugonem & hæredes, 1544). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=irk10DcsVqoC>.

²⁹³ Google Books, "Biblia Sacrosancta Testamenti Veteris et Novi...", visited 14 October 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=irk10DcsVqoC&pg=PA563>.

1545 ²⁹⁴	Luther Bibel ²⁹⁵	Auf einen jeglichten sabbather	296
1548	Leuvense Bijbel ²⁹⁷	op eenen dach vander sabbathen	298
1549	Bijbel (druk Christoffel Froschouer) ²⁹⁹	auf der sabbathen einen	300
1553	Coverdale Bible (Revised edition) ³⁰¹	Upon some Sabbath daye	302
1554	Testamenti Novi ³⁰³	Per vnā[m] sabbati ³⁰⁴	305

²⁹⁴ Note: The consulted 86th edition is not a pure reprint of Luther's 1545 edition but a reconstruction, as indicated in the preface: "Um aber diesen Bibel-Ausgabn die Uebersetzung lutheri in der möglichsten Richtigkeit zu liefern, lege der selige Stifter die von dem herrn D. Diectmann zu Stade im Jahr 1703 in 8vo herausgegebene Bibel zum Grunde, liesz aber dieselbe vorher mit fünf alten Bibeln, welche noch bey Lutheri Lebzeiten gedruckt worden, genau vergeleigen". (My own translation with additional note: However, to deliver this Bible edition of Luther's translation with the greatest possible accuracy, the blessed founder [= Carl Hildebrand, Frieherr von Canstein, c.f. preface page 4] had available an [octavo?] reissued Bible, published by D. Diectmann in Stade in the year 1703, but first compared it carefully with five older Bibles that were printed during Luther's lifetime.) Source: Internet Archive, "1545 Die Ganze Heilige Schrift Luther Bibel", visited 27 december 2021, <https://archive.org/details/1545DieGanzeHeiligeSchriftLutherBibel/page/n13/mode/2up>.

²⁹⁵ Martin Luther (übers.), *Die Bibel oder die gantze Heilige Schrift des alten und neuen Testaments, nach der deutschen übersetzung D. Martin Luthers*, LXXXVI. auflage (Halle: Cansteinischen Bibel-Anstalt, 1784). <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t0ns5c617>.

²⁹⁶ Internet Archive, "1545 Die Ganze Heilige Schrift Luther Bibel", visited 14 October 2021, <https://archive.org/stream/1545DieGanzeHeiligeSchriftLutherBibel/1545%20Die%20Ganze%20Heilige%20Schrift%20Luther%20Bibel#page/n1316/mode/1up>.

²⁹⁷ *Den gheheelen Bybel, Inhoudende het oude ende nieuwe Testament, met grooter naersticheyt ende arbeyt nv corts in duytsche van nyews ouerghestelt wt den Latijnschen ouden tekst ...* (Loeuen: Bartholomeus van Graue, 1548). <https://www.bijbelsdigitaal.nl/view/?mode=2&bible=leuvb1548>.

²⁹⁸ Nederlands-Vlaams Bijbelgenootschap, "Leuvense bijbel (1548): i. Totten Corinthien", visited 14 October 2021, <https://www.bijbelsdigitaal.nl/view/?mode=2&bible=leuvb1548&page=876&sub=1-2>.

²⁹⁹ *Das ander teil des alten Testaments mit sampt dem neüwen* (Zürich: Christoffel Froschouer, 1549). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=3L9IAAAAcAAJ>.

³⁰⁰ Google Books, "Bibel teutsch, das ist alle Bücher alts und nüws Testaments ..., Volume 2", visited 13 October 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=3L9IAAAAcAAJ&pg=RA14-PA7-IA1>.

³⁰¹ Myles Coverdale (trans.), *The Whole Byble, That is the holye Scripture, of the olde and new Testament, faithfuliye translated into Englysche by Myles Coverdale, ...* (London: Rycharde Ingge, 1553). <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t8hd95h2z>.

³⁰² Internet Archive, "The Coverdale Bible, revised edition of 1553", visited 14 October 2021, <https://archive.org/details/TheCoverdaleBibleRevisedEditionOf1553/page/n588/mode/1up>.

³⁰³ *Testamenti novi editio vulgata* (Lugduni: Theobaldum Paganum, 1554). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=9oaMScgal24C>.

³⁰⁴ Note: Matt. 28:1 reads 'in prima sabbati'.

³⁰⁵ Google Books, "Testamenti novi editio vulgata", visited 10 October 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=9oaMScgal24C&pg=RA1-PA82>.

1555	Del Nuouo Testamento ³⁰⁶	vn giorno de la settimana ³⁰⁷	308
1557	Bibel (Christoffel Froschouer ³⁰⁹)	Auff einen yede Sabbat	310
1558	La Sainte Bible ³¹¹	qu'un iour de Sabbath	312
1558	Bibbia del Malermi ³¹³	per vnu di della settimana	314
1558	Katholische Eck-Bibel ³¹⁵	auf der sabbath ain	316
1559	La Sainte Bible ³¹⁷	Cest quien un des sabbaths ³¹⁸	319
1559	Dietenberger Bibel ³²⁰	Auff der Sabbather einen ³²¹	322

³⁰⁶ *Del Nuouo Testamento di Iesu Christo Nostro Signore ...* (s.l.: Gio. Crispino, [1555]). <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t7tn1gr55>.

³⁰⁷ Comment: [?] [?] prim[o?].

³⁰⁸ Internet Archive, "Del Nuouo Testamento di Iesu Christo Nostro Signore, nuoua, e fedel traduttione dal testo greco in lingua volgare italiana ..", visited 15 October 2021, https://archive.org/details/bub_gb_d8ejkU2WhWQC/page/n529/mode/2up.

³⁰⁹ *Das gantz neüw Testament recht grundtlich verteütschet ...* (Zürych: Christoffel Froschouer, 1557). <https://doi.org/10.3931/e-rara-2013>.

³¹⁰ e-rara, the platform for digitized rare books from Swiss institutions, "ZB Zürich / Das gantz neüw Testament recht grundtlich verteütschet", visited 13 October 2021, <https://www.e-rara.ch/zuz/content/zoom/656398>.

³¹¹ *La Sainte Bible en François* (Lion: Sebastian Honeré, 1558). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=h1pXAAAAcAAJ>.

³¹² Google Books, "La Sainte Bible en François", visited 12 October 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=h1pXAAAAcAAJ&pg=RA5-PA179>.

³¹³ *Biblia volgare la qual in se contiene i sacrosanti libri del Vecchio, ...* (Vinegia: [Bernadino Bindoni?], 1558). https://books.google.nl/books?id=iRca_E-Er7UC.

³¹⁴ Google Books, "Biblia volgare la qual in se contiene i sacrosanti libri del Vecchio", visited 14 October 2021, https://books.google.nl/books?id=iRca_E-Er7UC&pg=PA376-IA1.

³¹⁵ Johannes Eck (übers.), *Alt und new Testament* (Ingolstadt: verlag Weissenhorn, 1558). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=e3FCAAAAacAAJ>.

³¹⁶ Google Books, "Bibel - Alt und new Testament", visited 13 October 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=e3FCAAAAacAAJ&pg=RA1-PR86>.

³¹⁷ *La Sainte Bible* (Lyon: Ian de Tovrnes, 1559). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=hZ1RAAAAacAAJ>.

³¹⁸ Note: on one of the sabbaths; at Matt. 28:1: ... le premier des iours du sabbath ... (English translation: the first of the days of the sabbath).

³¹⁹ Google Books, "La Sainte Bible", visited 10 October 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=hZ1RAAAAacAAJ&pg=RA4-PA148>.

³²⁰ Johan Dietenberger (übers.), *Das new Teltamēt nach alter in Chriftlicher Kyrchen geprauchter translation grundtlich und trewlich verteutfcht ...* (Cöln: Die Erbē Johan Quentels, 1559). <https://books.google.de/books?id=SJRHAAAacAA>. (N.b. the trailing dot is integral part of the URL).

³²¹ Comment (at Matt. 28:1): am abent aber der feier* tagen / welcher abricht am morgen des erstentags der Sabbathe. * des Sabbaths (English translation: In the evening, however, of the festival* days, which ends on the morning of the first day of the Sabbaths. *Sabbath). Source: Google Books, "Das new Testament ... verteutscht durch Johan Dietenberger", visited 14 October 2021, <https://books.google.de/books?id=SJRHAAAacAA.&pg=PA92>.

³²² Google Books, "Das new Testament ... verteutscht durch Johan Dietenberger", visited 14 October 2021, <https://books.google.de/books?id=SJRHAAAacAA.&pg=PA503>.

1560	Geneva Bible ³²³	Every first day of the weke ³²⁴	325
1560	Novum Testamentum (Beza) ³²⁶	primo quoq(ue) [die] hebdomadae	327
1560	Biestkensbijbel ³²⁸	op eenen yeghelijcken der Sabbathen	329
1562	Bibel (Christoffel Froschouer) ³³⁰	Auff der Sabbathen einen	331
1562	Deux-Aesbijbel ³³²	Op elcken eersten dach der weke ³³³	334
1563	La Bible (Geneva) ³³⁵	Chaque premier iour de la semaine ³³⁶	337

³²³ [Theodor Beza and John Calvin (trans.)], *The Bible and Holy Scriptures conteyned in the olde and newe Testament* (Geneva: Rouland Hall, 1560). <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t2n59pm35>.

³²⁴ Comment: Vpon the first day of the weke which [the] Scripture calleth de Lords day, others So[n]day, they accustomed not onely in[?] Church but at home also according to euery [??] zeale, to lay vp some piece of money towarde [the] relief of the poore brethere[n].

³²⁵ Internet Archive, "The Geneva Bible 1560", Visited 4 October 2021, <https://archive.org/details/TheGenevaBible1560/page/n1115/mode/2up>.

³²⁶ Beza, Théodore (trans.), *Tes kaines diathekes hapanta. Novum testamentum a Theodoro Beza versum cum eiusdem annotationibus* (Basileæ: Nicolaus Barbirius, 1560). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=oB1JAAAaAAJ>.

³²⁷ Google Books, "Tes kaines diathekes hapanta. Novum testamentum a Theodoro Beza", visited 14 October 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=oB1JAAAaAAJ&pg=PA565>.

³²⁸ *Den Bibel inhoudende dat Oude ende nieuwe Testament* (s.l.: Nicolaas Biestkens van Diest, 1560). <https://www.bijbelsdigitaal.nl/view/?mode=1&bible=biest1560>.

³²⁹ Nederlands-Vlaams Bijbelgenootschap, "Bieskensbijbel (1560)", visited 10 december 2021, <https://www.bijbelsdigitaal.nl/view/?mode=1&bible=biest1560&page=1024&sub=1-2>.

³³⁰ *Das gantz Neüw Testament/ grundtlich vnd wol verteütschet ...* ([Zürich] : Christoffel Froschouer, 1562). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=CWdRAAAaAAJ>.

³³¹ Google Books, "Das gantz Neüw Testament grundtlich vnd wol verteütschet", visited 13 October 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=CWdRAAAaAAJ&pg=PR251-IA1>.

³³² *Biblia: dat is, de gantsche Heylighe Schrift grondelick ende trouvelick verduytschet* (Embden: s.n., 1562). <https://www.bijbelsdigitaal.nl/view/?mode=2&bible=deuxa1562>.

³³³ Comment: dat is, Sondach (English translation: that is, the Sunday).

³³⁴ Nederlands-Vlaams Bijbelgenootschap, "Deux-Aesbijbel (1562): Sendtbrief Pauli Tot de Corinthen", visited 10 december 2021, <https://www.bijbelsdigitaal.nl/view/?mode=2&bible=deuxa1562&page=933&sub=1-2>.

³³⁵ [Theodor Beza, John Calvin (trans.)], *Le Nouveau Testament, c'est à dire, la Nouvelle Alliance de Nostre Seigneur Jesus Christ. Reueu & corrigé de nouveau sur le grec, par l'advis des ministres de Geneve* (Geneve: lean Bonne-foy, 1563). <https://n2t.net/ark:/12148/bpt6k108678p>.

³³⁶ Comment: Ou, quén chacun iour des Sabbaths (English translation: Or, on each day of the Sabbath).

³³⁷ Bibliothèque nationale de France, "Le Nouveau Testament, c'est à dire, la Nouvelle Alliance", visited 28 december 2021, <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k108678p/f497.item>.

1564	Testamenti Novi ³³⁸	Per vnam sabbati vnusquisq	339
1564	Franse Geneva Bijbel ³⁴⁰	premier iour de la semaine	341
1564	Dietenberger Bibel ³⁴²	Auff der Sabbather einen	343
1565	Bijbel Christoffel Froschouer ³⁴⁴	Auff einen yede Sabbat	345
1565	Beza ³⁴⁶	Primo qauque [die] hebdomadis	347
1566	La Bible ³⁴⁸	premier iour de la semaine	349
1568	Bishops Bible ³⁵⁰	Upon some sabboth daye	351
1569	Sagradas Escrituras Version Antigua ³⁵²	Cada primer sábado ³⁵³	354

³³⁸ *Testamenti Novi: Editio Vvlgata* (Lugduni: Haeredes Sebastian Gryphius, 1564). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=fL5fAAAAcAAJ>.

³³⁹ Google Books, "Testamenti Novi: Editio Vvlgata, visited 13 October 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=fL5fAAAAcAAJ&pg=PA451>.

³⁴⁰ *La Bible, qviest tovte la sainte escritvre* (Genève: François Jaquy, 1564). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=rOS7qiMkPKcC>.

³⁴¹ Google Books, "La Bible", visited 10 December 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=rOS7qiMkPKcC&pg=RA1-PA79>.

³⁴² Johan Dietenberger (übers.), *Daß New Testament/ nach Alter in Christlicher Kirchen gehabter Translation treulich verteutsch/ und mit vielen heilsamen Annotaten erleuchtt ...* (Cöln: Erben Johan Quentel und Gerwinum Calenius, 1564). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=imBCAAAAcAAJ>.

³⁴³ Google Books, "Daß New Testament: jetzo mit schönen ansehnlichen Figuren geziert", visited 11 October 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=imBCAAAAcAAJ&pg=PR107-IA1>.

³⁴⁴ *Das gantz neüw Testament recht grundtlich verteütschet ...* (Zürich: Christoffel Froschouer, 1565). <https://doi.org/10.3931/e-rara-5466>.

³⁴⁵ e-rara, the platform for digitized rare books from Swiss institutions, "ZB Zürich / Das gantz neüw Testament recht grundtlich verteütschet", visited 13 October 2021, <https://www.e-rara.ch/zuz/content/zoom/1659599>.

³⁴⁶ Theodore Beza (trans.), *Jesu Christi Domini nostri Novum Testamentum, sive Novum Foedus, cujus graeco contextui respondent interpretationes duae ...* ([Genève]: Héritiers d'Eustache Vignon, 1598). <https://doi.org/10.3931/e-rara-6871>.

³⁴⁷ e-rara, the platform for digitized rare books from Swiss institutions, "Bibliothèque de Genève / Jesu Christi Domini... [783]", visited 20 December 2021, https://www.e-rara.ch/gep_g/content/zoom/2025871.

³⁴⁸ *La Bible qve est tovte la sainte* (s.l.: Antoine Vincent, 1566). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=aVZXAAAAcAAJ>.

³⁴⁹ Google Books, "La Bible, Qvi Est Tovte La Sainte Escriture", visited 11 October 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=aVZXAAAAcAAJ&pg=RA1-PA154>.

³⁵⁰ [Matthew Parker (trans.)?], *The Holie Bible conteynyng the olde Testament and the Newe* ([London?]: [Richard Jugge?], [1568]). <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t0rr5jj4t>.

³⁵¹ Internet Archive, "1568 The Bishop's Bible", visited 10 October 2021, <https://archive.org/details/1568TheBishopsBible/page/n1525/mode/2up>.

³⁵² Casiodoro de Reina (trad.), "Las Sagradas Escrituras Version Antigua Traducida de los Textos Originales en Hebreo y Griego al Español por Casiodoro de Reina (1569)" in *Sagradas Escrituras Version Antigua*, edited by Russell Martin Stendal (s.l.: Project Gutenberg, 2004). <https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/6528>.

³⁵³ Note: literally 'on every first Saturday/Sabbath' probably understood as 'Sunday'.

³⁵⁴ The Project Gutenberg, "The Project Gutenberg eBook, Sagradas Escrituras Version Antigua, by Russell Martin Stendal", visited 27 December 2021, <https://www.gutenberg.org/cache/epub/6528/pg6528-images.html#id29224>.

1569	Biblia de Casiodoro de Reina (Biblia del Oso) ³⁵⁵	Cada primer dia de la semana ³⁵⁶	357
1571	Novum Testamentum (Erasmus) ³⁵⁸	in una sabbatorum	359
1582	Rheims Bijbel ³⁶⁰ (contrareformatie bijbel) ³⁶¹	the first of the sabbath ³⁶²	363
1584	Duitse Bijbel ³⁶⁴	Auff der Sabbathen einen	365
1588	Bible Geneve (Français) ³⁶⁶	premier iour de la semaine	367

³⁵⁵ [Casiodoro de Reina (trad.)], *La Biblia, Qve Es, Los Sacros Libros Del Vieio Y Nvevo Testamento: Traslada en Español* ([Basel]: [T. Guarinus], 1569). <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t1qg1j41p>.

³⁵⁶ Note: literally 'every first day of the week'.

³⁵⁷ Internet Archive, "La Biblia, Qve Es, Los Sacros Libros Del Vieio Y Nvevo Testamento", visited 10 October 2021, <https://archive.org/details/labibliaqveeslos00rein/page/n1203/mode/1up>.

³⁵⁸ Desiderus Erasmus (trans.), *Novvm Testamentvm Iesv Christi, Græce et Latinè* (Basileæ: Hæredes Nicolai Bryling, 1571). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=xyg6AAAAcAAJ>.

³⁵⁹ Google Books, "Novum Testamentum Jesu Christi", visited 18 October 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=xyg6AAAAcAAJ&pg=PA536>.

³⁶⁰ John Cousturier (trans.), *Holy Bible Faithfvly Translated Into English: Ovt of the Authentical Latin, Diligently Conferred with the Hebrew, Greek, and Other Editions in Diuers Languages* (Rheims: John Fogny, 1582). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=kofWAAAAMAAJ>.

³⁶¹ Note: This is evident, among other things, from the text on the title page ('and especially for the dicourerie of the corruptions of viuerse late translations'). Source: Google Books, "Holy Bible Faithfvly Translated Into English", visited 11 October 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=kofWAAAAMAAJ&pg=PP5>.

³⁶² Comment: That is su[n]day. *Hiero. q.[?]. Hedibia*. So quickly did the Christians keepe Sunday, holiday, and assembled to Diuine Seruice on the same.

³⁶³ Google Books, "Holy Bible Faithfvly Translated Into English", visited 11 October 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=kofWAAAAMAAJ&pg=PA467>.

³⁶⁴ *Das gantz Neüw Testament / grundtlich und wol verteütschet, auch geziert mit vil schönen und notwendigen Concordantzen ...* (Zürych: Christoffel Froschouer, 1584). <https://doi.org/10.3931/e-rara-8223>.

³⁶⁵ e-rara, the platform for digitized rare books from Swiss institutions, "ZB Zürich / Das gantz Neüw Testament", visited 13 October 2021, <https://www.e-rara.ch/zuz/content/zoom/2141988>.

³⁶⁶ Jean Calvin et Théodore de Bèze (trad.), *La Bible, qui est tovnt la saincte escritvre dv vieil & du Nouveau Testament ...* (Genève: Jérémie Des Boards, 1588). <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t4sk2m43b>.

³⁶⁷ Internet Archive, "Bible Geneve 1588 (Français)", visited 14 October 2021, https://archive.org/details/bible_geneve_1588/page/n1197/mode/2up.

1590	Dietenberger Bibel ^{368,369}	Auff der Sabbather einen	370
1592	Clementine Vulgate ³⁷¹	Per unam sabbati	372
1595	Geneva Bible ³⁷³	Every first day of the weeke	374
[1596?]	La Sainte Bible ³⁷⁵	premier iour de la samaine	376
1598	Novum Testamentum (Beza) ³⁷⁷	Primo quoque [die] hebdomadis	378
1606	Geneva Bible ³⁷⁹	Every first day of the weeke ³⁸⁰	381

³⁶⁸ Johan Dietenberger (übers.), *Bibell, das ist, alle Bücher alts und news Testaments/ nach Alter in Christlicher Kirchen gehabter Translation trewlich verteutsch* ... (Cöln: Gerqinus Calenius, 1590). <https://books.google.de/books?id=17dIAAAcAAJ>.

³⁶⁹ Note: It is clear from the preface that this Bible must be considered part of the Counter-Reformation: "(...) Nachdem sich in difen letzten und gefערlichen zeiten/ viel und mancherlen Spaltungen in Teutfcher Nation/ den Glauben und unfere heilige Religion betreffend/ durch etliche viel pfeudochriften/ Sectenmeifter/ falsche brüder und Propheten/ wie der herr vorgefagt/ erregt und erhebt habe/ (etc.)". (English translation: After, in these recent and dangerous times, many and various divisions in the German nation concerning faith and our holy religion have been stirred up and raised by several pseudo-Christians, sect leaders, false brothers, and prophets, as the Lord foretold ...). Source: Google Books, "Das new Testament ... verteutsch durch Johan Dietenberger", visited 14 October 2021, <https://books.google.de/books?id=17dIAAAcAAJ&pg=PP7>.

³⁷⁰ Google Books, "Bibell, das ist, alle Bücher alts und news Testaments verteutsch", visited 14 October 2021, <https://books.google.de/books?id=17dIAAAcAAJ&hl=de&pg=RA2-PA93>.

³⁷¹ *Biblia sacra vulgatae editionis* (Romæ: Typographia Apostolica Vaticana, 1592). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=slwgf1mnU0UC>.

³⁷² Google Books, "Biblia sacra vulgatae editionis", visited 18 December 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=slwgf1mnU0UC&pg=PA1056>.

³⁷³ *The Bible: that is, the Holy Scriptures contened in the Olde and New Testament. Translated according to the Ebrew and Greeke,....* (London: Christopher Barker, 1595). <https://www.originalbibles.com/geneva-bible-with-tomson-new-testament-1595-pdf>.

³⁷⁴ Original Bibles, "Geneva Bible With Tomson New Testament 1595 PDF", visited 10 December 2021, <https://www.originalbibles.com/geneva-bible-with-tomson-new-testament-1595-pdf/>, 1019.

³⁷⁵ [*La sainte Bible*] (s.l.: [lean Pillehotte?], [1596?]). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=sx5MM9aQioC>.

³⁷⁶ Google Books, "La Sainte Bible...", visited 13 October 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=-sx5MM9aQioC&pg=RA1-PA138>.

³⁷⁷ Theodore Beza (trans.), *Jesu Christi Domini nostri Novum Testamentum, sive Novum Foedus, cujus graeco contextui respondent interpretationes duae: una, Vetus: altera, Theodori Bezae Ejusdem Th. Bezae annotationes ...* (Genève: Héritiers d'Eustache Vignon, 1598). <https://doi.org/10.3931/e-rara-6871>.

³⁷⁸ e-rara, the platform for digitized rare books from Swiss institutions, "Bibliothèque de Genève / Jesu Christi Domini...", visited 13 december 2021, https://www.e-rara.ch/gep_g/content/zoom/2025871.

³⁷⁹ *The Bible Translated according to the Ebrew and Greeke, and conferred with the best translations in diuers languages. ...* (London: Robert Barker, 1606). <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t2f77nd6k>.

³⁸⁰ Comment: Vpon the first day of the weeke, which the Scripture calleth de Lords day, others Sunday, they accustomed not only in the Church, but at home also according to euery mans zeale, to lay vp some piece of money toward the reliefe of the poore brethren.

³⁸¹ Internet Archive, "Geneva Bible", visited 27 December 2021, <https://archive.org/details/ost-english-bible00lond/page/n1111/mode/2up>.

1608	Il Nvovo Testamento ³⁸²	Ogni *primo giorno della settimana ³⁸³	384
1611	Katholische Eck-bibel ³⁸⁵	Auf den Sabbath ³⁸⁶	387
1611	King James Version ³⁸⁸	Upon the first day of the week	389
1618	Katholische Eck-Bibel ³⁹⁰	Auff den Sabbath	391
1633	Rhemes New Testament ³⁹²	In the first of the Sabboth ³⁹³	394
1629	Zuricher NT ³⁹⁵	Je auff den ersten tag der wochen	396

³⁸² Giovanni Diodati (trad.), *IL Nvovo Testamento del Signor nostro Iesv Christo* (s.l.: s.n., 1608). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=AcNIAAAAcAAJ>.

³⁸³ Comment: Fat. 20,7. *Apoc.* 1,10.

³⁸⁴ Google Books, "Il nuovo testamento di Jesu Christo tradotto da da Giovanni Diodati", visited 13 December 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=AcNIAAAAcAAJ&pg=PA445>.

³⁸⁵ Johannes Eck (übers.), *Bibel Alt unnd New Testament/ Nach dem Text in der H. Kirchen gebraucht: ...*, editiert bei Tobiam Hendschelium (Cölln: Bernard Wolter, 1611). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=Mww0grSvXwkC>.

³⁸⁶ Note: there are no footnotes here, but the rendering "Sabbath" in practice should be understood as referring to Sunday.

³⁸⁷ Google Books, "Bibel Alt unnd New Testament. Nach dem Text in der H. Kirchen gebraucht", visited 14 October 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=Mww0grSvXwkC&pg=RA1-PA166>.

³⁸⁸ *The Holy Bible, conteyning the Old Testament, and the new: Newly Translated out of the Originall tongues: ...* (London: Robert Barker, 1611). <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t7vm5rc2k>.

³⁸⁹ Internet Archive, "The Holy Bible, Conteyning the Old Testament and the New", visited 27 December 2021, <https://archive.org/details/Bible1611/page/n1413/mode/2up>.

³⁹⁰ Johannes Eck (übers.), *Bibel, alt unnd new Testament nach dem text in der H. Kirchen gebraucht*, editiert bei Tobiam Hendschelium (Cölln: Bernard Wolter, 1619). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=LixJAAAAcAAJ>.

³⁹¹ Google Books, "Bibel, alt unnd new Testament ... erstlich durch Johan Ecken auff ...", visited 13 October 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=LixJAAAAcAAJ&pg=RA1-PA166>.

³⁹² English College of Rheims (trans.), *The New Testament of Iesus Christ: faithfully translated into English, out of the authentical Latin, diligently conferred with the Greek, & other editions in divers languages ...* ([Rouen?]: Iohn Covstvier, 1633). <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t3st7sd4h>.

³⁹³ Comment: That is Sunday. *Hiero. q. 4. Hedibiae*. So quickly did the Christians keepe Sunday, holiday, and assembled to Diuine Seruice on the same.

³⁹⁴ Internet Archive, "The New Testament of Iesus Christ : faithfully translated into English", visited 10 December 2021, <https://archive.org/details/newtestamentofie00engl/page/422/mode/2up>.

³⁹⁵ *Das gantz Neüw Testament unsers Herren und Heylands Jesu Christi: Recht grundtlich nach der Griechischen Hauptspraach verteütscht, und mit Fleiss widerumb ubersehen* (Zürich: Johann Jacob Bodmer, 1629). <https://doi.org/10.3931/e-rara-10484>.

³⁹⁶ e-rara, the platform for digitized rare books from Swiss institutions, "ZB Zürich / Das gantz Neüw Testament", visited 12 October 2021, <https://www.e-rara.ch/zuz/content/zoom/3121072>.

1637	Staten Vertaling ³⁹⁷	Op elcken ³⁹⁸ eersten [dagh] ³⁹⁹ der weke	400
1642	Novum Testamentum (Beza) ⁴⁰¹	Primo quoque <i>die</i> hebdomadis ⁴⁰²	403
1648	Lutherse vertaling ⁴⁰⁴	Op elcken eersten dagh der Sabbathen	405
1667	Zuricher NT (revidiert) ⁴⁰⁶	Je auf den ersten tag der wochen	407

³⁹⁷ *Biblia, dat is: De gantsche H. Schrifture, vervattende alle de Canonijcke Boecken des Ouden en des Nieuwen Testaments* (s.l.: Paulus Aertsz. van Ravensteyn, 1637). <https://www.bijbelsdigitaal.nl/view/?bible=sv1637>.

³⁹⁸ Comment (original footnote #6 referring to the next following word): *Gr.* eenen. Hebr. siet diergelijcke wijze van spreke[n], Gen. 1.5. Dan. 9.1. siet oock Matt. 28.1. Marc. 16.9. Luc. 24.1. (English translation from old Dutch: Gr[reek]. one. Hebr[aism]. see a similar way of speaking in Genesis 1:5 and Daniel 9:1. Also see Matthew 28:1, Mark 16:9, and Luke 24:1) Note that the reference to Daniel 9:1 point to the Hebrew *בְּשַׁבָּת אֶחָת*, which is translated in the LXX as *ἕτους πρώτου ἐπι*.

³⁹⁹ Comment (original footnote #7): *Gr.* der Sabbathen, waer door de geheele weke dickwils wort genoemt. siet Mar. 16.9. Ioan. 20.1. Dese eerste dagh, wordt van Ioanne genaemt des Heeren dagh, Apocal. 1.10. om dat de Heere Christus op dien dagh van den dooden is opgestaen. Op desen dagh plegen de Apostelen hare vergaderinghen te houden. Ioan. 20. versen 19, 26. Actor. 20.7. (English translation from old Dutch: Gr[reek]. the Sabbaths, which often refers to the entire week. See Mark 16:9 and John 20:1. This first day is called by John 'the Lord's Day' (Revelation 1:10) because the Lord Christ rose from the dead on that day. On this day, the Apostles customarily held their meetings. See John 20:19, 26 and Acts 20:7).

⁴⁰⁰ Nederlands-Vlaams Bijbelgenootschap, "Statenvertaling (1637): De I. Sendt-brief Pauli aen die van Corinthen", visited 10 December 2021, <https://www.bijbelsdigitaal.nl/view/?bible=sv1637&page=1154&mode=1>.

⁴⁰¹ Theodore Beza (trans.), *Jesu Christi Domini Nostri Novum Testamentum, sive, Novum Foedus: cujus Graeco contextui respondent interpretationes duae, una vetus, altera Theodori Bezae ...* (Cantabrigiae: Ex Officina Rogeri Danielis, 1642). <https://catalog.hathitrust.org/Record/009037958/Home>.

⁴⁰² Note: This edition contains an extensive justification for their translation choices.

⁴⁰³ HathiTrust Digital Library, "Jesu Christi Domini Nostri Novum Testamentum, sive, Novum", visited 12 December 2021, <https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=njp.32101078251947&view=1up&seq=556>.

⁴⁰⁴ Maarten Luther (vert.), *BIBLIA, Dat is, De gantsche H. Schrifture, vervattende alle de Boecken des Ouden ende Nieuwen TESTAMENTS: Nu Van nieuws uijt D. M. Luthers Hoogh-Duijtsche Bibel in onse Neder-landsche tale getrouwelijck over-geset, ...* (Amsterdam: Rieuwert Dircksz van Baardt, [1648]). <https://www.bijbelsdigitaal.nl/view/?mode=1&bible=luthv1648>.

⁴⁰⁵ Nederlands-Vlaams Bijbelgenootschap, "Lutherse vertaling (1648): De Send-brief Pauli aen de Corinthiers", visited 10 December 2021, <https://www.bijbelsdigitaal.nl/view/?mode=1&bible=luthv1648&ref=1Cor.16>.

⁴⁰⁶ *Biblia: Das ist, Alle Bücher der heiligen Schrift : Auss den Grundsprachen treulich und wol verteutschet, aufs neue, und mit fleiss widerum übersehen ...* (Zürich: Johann Jacob und Heinrich Bodmer, 1667). <https://doi.org/10.3931/e-rara-9984>.

⁴⁰⁷ e-rara, the platform for digitized rare books from Swiss institutions, "ZB Zürich / Biblia: Das ist, Alle Bücher der heiligen Schrift", visited 12 October 2021, <https://www.e-rara.ch/zuz/content/zoom/2937483>.

1687	Bibel (Christoffel Froschouer) ⁴⁰⁸	Je auf den ersten tag der wochen	409
1713	Emster Bibel ⁴¹⁰	auf der sabbather eine	411
1729	Die Heilige Schriff ⁴¹²	Auf einen jeglichen Sabbather ⁴¹³	414
1729	Daniel Mace's New Testament (diglot) ⁴¹⁵	every sabbath-day ⁴¹⁶	417
1764	Anthony Purver translation ⁴¹⁸	At the first [Day] after the Sabbath	419

⁴⁰⁸ *Das Neue Testament unsers Herren und Heilands / recht grundlich nach der griechischen Haupt-Sprache verteutschet und mit Fleiss übersehen* (Zürich: Eustachio Froschauer, 1687). <https://doi.org/10.3931/e-rara-13315>.

⁴⁰⁹ e-rara, the platform for digitized rare books from Swiss institutions, "ZB Zürich / Das Neue Testament...", visited 12 October 2021, <https://www.e-rara.ch/zuz/content/zoom/4043951>.

⁴¹⁰ Hieronymum Embser (übers.), *Das neue Testament durch den hochgelehrten Herrn Hieronymum Embser treulich verteutschet* (s.l.: Joseph Schlögel, 1713). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=ryxJAAAAcAAJ>.

⁴¹¹ Google Books, "Das neue Testament durch Hieronymum Embser ... verteutschet", visited 14 October 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=ryxJAAAAcAAJ&pg=PA538>.

⁴¹² Martin Luther (übers.), *Die Heilige Schriff Neuen Testaments nach der fürtrefflichen übersetzung und mit den vorreden auch Rand-Glossen D. Martin Luthers*, editiert bei Johann Christian Klemm. (Tübingen: Johann Georg und Christian Gottfried Cotta, 1729). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=5d5dAAAAcAAJ>.

⁴¹³ Comment: Auf einen oder ersten der Sabbather, d.i. Wochen Tage, Matth. 28,1. Marc. 16,2.9. Luc. 24,1. Joh. 20,1.19. Er versthehet den Sonn, oder des Herrn Tag, da sollen sie sammeln, und ist also die heiligung unsers Sabbaths oder des ersten Tags in der Wochen eine Apostolische Anordnung. (translation: On 'one of,' or 'the first of' the Sabbaths, that is, the week days, Matt. 28:1, Mark 16:2,9, Luke 24:1, John 20:1,19. He understood [this] as the Sunday, or the Lord's Day, when they should gather, and thus the sanctification of our Sabbath or [in the sense: 'also known as'] the first day of the week is an Apostolic ordinance.)

⁴¹⁴ Google Books, "Die Heilige Schriff Neuen Testaments", visited 14 October 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=5d5dAAAAcAAJ&pg=PA419>.

⁴¹⁵ Daniel Mace (trans.), *New Testament (1729)*, e-Sword® module (s.l: bible-support.com, 2011). <http://www.bible-support.com/e-sword-downloads/file/2639-daniel-mace-new-testament-1729bblxexe>. Note: No facsimile was found for this specific source. The presented data was taken from: [Daniel Mace (trans.)], *The New Testament in Greek and English, Containing the Original Text Corrected from the Authority of the most Authentic Manuscripts: ...* (London: for J. Roberts, 1729).

⁴¹⁶ Note: Daniel Mace was Presbyterian, and therefore by mentioning 'sabbath-day' he actually referred to the 'Christian sabbat' (=Sunday).

⁴¹⁷ Daniel Mace, *New Testament (1729)*, e-Sword® module, 1 Kor. 16:2.

⁴¹⁸ Anthony Purver (trans.), *A New and Literal Translation of All the Books of the Old and New Testament with notes, Critical and Explanatory* (London: W. Richardson and S. Clark, 1764). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=qIZaAAAAYAAJ>.

⁴¹⁹ Google Books, "A New and Literal Translation of All the Books of the Old and New ..., Volume 2", visited 16 October 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=qIZaAAAAYAAJ&pg=RA2-PA225>.

1776	Dietenberger Bibel ⁴²⁰	Auff der Sabbather einen	421
1784	Luther Bijbel ⁴²²	Auf einen jeglichen sabbather	423
1809	MacKnight literal translation ⁴²⁴	On the first DAY of every week	425
1855	Elbefeller Bibel ⁴²⁶	An jedem ersten Wochentage	427
1864	Empatic diaglott Bible ⁴²⁸	† ⁴²⁹ Every † First Day of the week	430
1867 ⁴³¹	Darby Translation ⁴³²	On [the] first of [the] week	433

⁴²⁰ Johan Dietenberger (übers.), *Das Neue Testament, nach alter in christlicher kirche gehabter translation getreu verdeutschet ...* (Augsburg: Matthaus Rieger, 1776). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=VAY7AAAAcAAJ>.

⁴²¹ Google Books, "Biblia sacra, Das ist: Die ganze Heilige Schrift alten und neuen ..., Volume 5", visited 14 October 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=VAY7AAAAcAAJ&pg=PA229>.

⁴²² Martin Luther (übers.), *Die Bibel: oder die ganze heilige Schrift des alten und neuen Testaments, ...* (Halle: s.n., 1784). <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t74t7338b>.

⁴²³ Internet Archive, "Die Bibel: oder die ganze heilige Schrift des alten und neuen Testaments", visited 10 December 2021, <https://archive.org/details/diebibeloderdieg00luth/page/212/mode/2up>.

⁴²⁴ James MacKnight (trans.), *A new literal translation from the original Greek of all the apostolical epistles ...* (London: Longman, Hurst, Rees, and Orme, 1809). <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t02z1bj93>.

⁴²⁵ Internet Archive, "A new literal translation from the original Greek of all the apostolical epistles", visited 15 October 2021, <https://archive.org/details/newliteraltransl01mack/page/653/mode/1up>.

⁴²⁶ *Neue Übersetzung des zweiten Theiles der heiligen Schrift genannt Neues Testament aus dem Urtext übersetzt von einigen Christen, 1^e auflage, teil 2* (Elberfeld: Sam Lucas, 1855). <https://www.cw-archive.org/de/books/18-elberfelder-uebersetzung-neues-testament-1855-1-auflage-teil-2>.

⁴²⁷ Christian Writings Archive, "Elberfelder Übersetzung, Neues Testament, 1855 (1. Auflage), Teil 2", visited 30 December 2021, <https://www.cw-archive.org/de/books/18-elberfelder-uebersetzung-neues-testament-1855-1-auflage-teil-2#165>.

⁴²⁸ Benjamin Wilson (trans.), *The Emphatic Diaglott containing the Original Greek tekst of what is commonly styled the New Testament ...* (New York: Wowler & Wells Co. 1864). <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t6543090j>.

⁴²⁹ Comment: As *kata polin* signifies Every city; and *kata meena*, every month; and Acts xiv. 23, *kata ekkleesian*, in every church; so *kata mian sabbatoon* signifies the first day of every week.— *Macknight*.

⁴³⁰ Internet Archive, "The emphatic diaglott: containing the original Greek text of what is commonly styled the New Testament", visited 10 December 2021, <https://archive.org/details/emphaticdiaglott00wils/page/n563/mode/2up>.

⁴³¹ Note: This is the year of first publication. The scan is from the second publication (1872). According: Bible Research by Michael Marlowe, "John Nelson Darby's Version", visited 13 December 2021, <http://www.bible-researcher.com/darby.html>.

⁴³² John Nelson Darby (trans.), *The Gospels, Act, Epistles and Book of Revelation commonly called: The New Testament*, second edition, revised (London: G. Morrish, s.a.). <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t72v3k962>.

⁴³³ Internet Archive, "Darby's Writings: New Translation New Testament & Synopsis Books Bible multi vols.", visited 10 December 2021, <https://archive.org/details/DarbysWritingsNewTranslationNewTestamentSynopsisBooksBibleMulti/00.2.NewTranslNT.GospActsEpistBkRev.DarbyJN.CritNotes.Index.2ndrev.Lon.GMor.1867./page/n293/mode/2up>.

1876	Julia E. Smith Parker translation ⁴³⁴	According to one day of the sabbaths	435
1876	Luther Bibel ⁴³⁶	Auf je der Sabbather einen	437
1880	Luther Bibel (American Bibel-Gesellschaft) ⁴³⁸	Auf einen jeglichen Sabbather	439
1882	Luther Bibel ⁴⁴⁰	Auf einen jeglichen Sabbather	441
1896	Tischendorf ⁴⁴²	Upon the first [day] of the week	443
1900	Luther Bibel ⁴⁴⁴	Auf jeglichen ersten Tag der Woche ⁴⁴⁵	446
1903	Luther Bibel (Amerikaans) ⁴⁴⁷	Auf je der Sabbather einen	448

⁴³⁴ Julia E. Smith (trans.), *The Holy Bible: Containing the Old and New Testaments translated literally from the original tongues* (Hartford, Conn.: American Publishing Company, 1876). <https://books.google.nl/books?id=03gdC1EPvEMC>.

⁴³⁵ Google Books, "The Holy Bible: Containing the Old and New Testaments", visited 13 December 2021, <https://books.google.nl/books?id=03gdC1EPvEMC&pg=RA2-PA192>.

⁴³⁶ Martin Luther (übers.), *Die Bibel oder die ganze Heilige Schrift des Alten und Neuen Testaments* (Nürnberg: Privilegirter Central-Bibel-Verein, 1876). <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t5db99c9r>.

⁴³⁷ Internet Archive, "Die Bibel oder die ganze Heilige Schrift ...", visited 20 December 2021, <https://archive.org/details/diebibeloderdieg0000luth/page/213/mode/1up>.

⁴³⁸ Martin Luther (übers.), *Das Neue Testament unsers Herrn und Heilandes Jesu Christi* (New York: American Bibel-Gesellschaft, 1880). <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t2d79rk70>.

⁴³⁹ Internet Archive, "Das Neue Testament unsers Herrn ...", visited 20 December 2021, <https://archive.org/details/dasneuetestament00luth/page/198/mode/2up>.

⁴⁴⁰ Martin Luther (übers.), *Die Bibel: oder die ganze Heilige Schrift des Alten und Neuen Testaments ...* (Cöln: Britische und ausländische Bibelgesellschaft, 1882). <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t3514js0z>.

⁴⁴¹ Internet Archive, "Die Bibel : oder die ganze Heilige Schrift des Alten und Neuen Testaments", visited 20 December 2021, <https://archive.org/details/diebibeloderdieg00luthuoft/page/148/mode/2up>.

⁴⁴² Constantine Tischendorf (trans.), *The New testament: the authorised English version; with introduction, and various readings* (Leipzig: Bernhard Tauchnitz, 1869). <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t0jt0971c>.

⁴⁴³ Internet Archive, "Tischendorf. V. Various Works. Codicis, Synoptics, Testaments, Anecdotes, Criticism. 12vols.1845-1880", visited 10 December 2021, <https://archive.org/details/Tischendorf.V.Various/09.NewTestAuthorizedEngVers.Tischen.dorf.TauchnitzEdvol1000.1869./page/n305/mode/2up>.

⁴⁴⁴ Martin Luther (übers.), *Die Bibel; oder, Die ganze Heilige Schrift des Alten und Neuen Testaments, nach der deutschen übersetzung D. Martin Luthers. Im auftrage des Deutschen evangelischen kirchenkonferenz durchgesehene ausgabe, 1^e abdruck* (Halle a. S.: Cansteinschen Bibelanstalt, 1900). <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t46q2jt9g>.

⁴⁴⁵ Comment: Apg. 20:7 (= Acts 20:7).

⁴⁴⁶ Internet Archive, "Die Bibel oder die ganze Heilige Schrift des Alten und Neuen Testaments ...", visited 28 December 2021, <https://archive.org/details/diebibeloderdie01kirccoog/page/227/mode/2up>.

⁴⁴⁷ Martin Luther (übers.), *Die Bibel, oder, die ganze Heilige Schrift Alten und Neuen Testaments nach der deutschen übersetzung Dr. Martin Luther* (St. Louis, Mo: Concordia Publishing House, 1903). <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t9b622654>.

⁴⁴⁸ Internet Archive, "Die Bibel, oder, die ganze Heilige Schrift Alten und Neuen Testaments", visited 28 December 2021, <https://archive.org/details/LutherBibleCPH1903/page/n1297/mode/2up>.

1906	Luther Bibel ⁴⁴⁹	Auf jeglichen ersten Tag der Woche ⁴⁵⁰	451
1912	Luther Bibel ⁴⁵²	An jeglichem ersten Tag der Woche ⁴⁵³	454
1986	Neo Vulgaat ⁴⁵⁵	Per primam sabbati	456

Table 1: Overview of historical translations

⁴⁴⁹ Martin Luther (übers.), *Die Bibel oder die ganze Heilige Schrift des Alten und Neuen Testaments nach der deutschen übersetzung D. Martin Luther. Durchgesehen im Auftrag der Deutschen Evangelischen Kirchenconferentz* (Berlin: Britische und ausländische Bibelgesellschaft, 1906). <https://n2t.net/ark:/13960/t6639rc2r>.

⁴⁵⁰ Comment: Apg. 20:7 (= Acts 20:7).

⁴⁵¹ Internet Archive, "Die Bibel: Martin Luther", visited 28 December 2021, <https://archive.org/details/diebibeloderdie01unkngoog/page/n1326/mode/2up>.

⁴⁵² Martin Luther (übers.), *Die Bibel oder die ganze Heilige Schrift des Alten und Neuen Testaments. Textfassung 1912* (Stuttgart: Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 1982).

⁴⁵³ Comment: Apg. 20:7 (= Acts 20:7).

⁴⁵⁴ Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, "1. Korinther 16 - Lutherbibel 1912 (LU12) - die-bibel.de", visited 10 December 2021, <https://www.die-bibel.de/bibeln/online-bibeln/lesen/LU12/1CO.16/1.-Korinther-16>.

⁴⁵⁵ *Nova Vulgata Bibliorum Sacrorum Editio*, Editio Typica Altera (Vatican City: Libreria Editrice Vaticana, 1986).

⁴⁵⁶ *Ibid.*, 2157.

APPENDIX 2: TEXTUAL WITNESSES

Several Greek-language manuscripts from the first five centuries serve as textual witnesses to 1 Cor. 16. Consequentially, several textual variants are known. In the context of this thesis, the occurrence of two important variants within the first clause of verse 2, is of particular importance: the plural form *κατὰ μίαν σαββάτων* and the singular form *κατὰ μίαν σαββάτου*. The text-critical edition commonly used in academic research, the Nestle-Aland 28th edition (NA28),⁴⁵⁷ is based on the singular form *κατὰ μίαν σαββάτου*. Regarding the textual reading of 1 Cor.16:2^a this thesis deliberately used the plural form *κατὰ μίαν σαββάτων*. Since a major part of this thesis concerns historical research, it is important to use as a starting point the reading that was common during the period covered by the research. During the period of the translation change, the plural form was most certainly prevalent. The same plural form appeared among the commentators of early church history. The choice made is therefore logical, well-defensible, and even enforced within the first two historically oriented parts.

It can be argued that a choice to use the plural form can influence the meaning of the idiom under investigation. That is correct, and therefore a choice for the plural form requires further explanation. One of the premises for why *κατὰ μίαν σαββάτων* would mean 'every first day of the week' on grammatical grounds is the assumption that, regarding the lemma *σαββάτων*, the plural form and singular form are functionally interchangeable. This position is inspired by the fact that six other verses,⁴⁵⁸ which are translated 'first day of the week,' contain the plural morphological form *μίαν σαββάτων*, which, according to the prevalent frame of reference, is understood as a singular form. A singular morphological form *μίαν σαββάτου* in 1 Cor. 16:2^a, considered in isolation, seems supportive of an understanding as 'first day of the week', but simultaneously undermines other underlying assumptions. First, attributing strong importance to a singular form in 1 Cor. 16:2^a constitutes an implicit acknowledgment that there is indeed a difference in meaning between the singular and plural form. Additionally, a singular form in 1 Cor. 16:2^a will weaken the similarity of form with the other 6 verses which serve as substantiation for the supposed similarity of meaning. The above alone already shows that the assumption that the plural form and the singular form (in these instances) are interchangeable holds some inconsistency. On this ground, supplemented with the other arguments brought forth in this thesis, it is more logical to assume an actual difference in meaning between the plural form and the singular form.

The observation that there is most likely a difference in meaning between singular and plural forms raises the question of which form Paul actually used in

⁴⁵⁷ Aland, Barbara and Kurt (ed.), *Novum Testamentum Graece*, 28th Revised Edition (Stuttgart: Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 2012).

⁴⁵⁸ Matt. 28:1, Mark 16:2, Luke. 24:1, John 20:1&19, and Acts 20:7. The reference in the 'long ending of Mark' is disregarded due to the use of a different idiom.

his letter to the Corinthians. Complete certainty about this cannot be obtained. Barbara Aland confirms this in connection with the text-critical Nestle-Aland edition:

It is important that the users of the *Editio Critica Maior* and of the Nestle always keep in mind that the text line of our edition does not claim to be the original text. This text is lost and cannot be reconstructed.⁴⁵⁹

For this study, two textual variants of 1 Cor.16:2^a are considered important. While the *Textus Receptus* textual family uses the plural form, later text-critical editions⁴⁶⁰ — all of which arose after the translation 'every first day of the week' took hold — contain the singular form. However, as shown in Table 2 and the discussion that follows, the plural form has good and early textual witnesses. To facilitate a comparison, the table will show, for all eight New Testament verses in which the translation "first day of the week" occurs today, which form(s) of the lemma *σάββατον* is used by the relevant text witness. Note that the three codices in this table have uncial script that is presented here (for the sake of readability and simplicity of comparison with the NA28 text) in lower case. The last two columns show, respectively, the text according to NA28 and an indication of whether the text-critical apparatus reports textual variants for the specific text section examined.

Location	Sinaiticus (Ⲱ) Saec.IV ¹	Alexandrinus (A) Saec.V ¹	Vaticanus (B) Saec.IV ¹	NA28	NA28 variants
Matt. 28:1 ¹	σαββάτων ¹	σαββατων ¹	σαββάτων ¹	σαββάτων	no
Mark. 16:2	σαββάτων ¹	σαββάτων	σαββάτων ¹	σαββάτων	multiple
Mark. 16:9	absent	σαββάτου ¹	absent	σαββάτου	???
Luke 24:1	σαββάτων ¹	σαββάτων	σαββάτων	σαββάτων	no
John 20:1	σαββάτων ¹	σαββάτων	σαββάτων	σαββάτων	no
John 20:19	σαββάτων ¹	σαββάτων	σαββάτων	σαββάτων	no
Acts. 20:7	σαββάτων ¹	σαββάτων	σαββάτων	σαββάτων	no
1 Cor. 16:2	σαββάτω ¹ σαββάτων σαββάτου? ¹	σαββάτου ¹	σαββάτου ¹ σαββάτων? ^(D)	σαββάτου	Yes

Table 2: Overview of text witnesses

⁴⁵⁹ Aland, B., "New Testament Textual Research, Its Methods and Its Goals" in SE Porter & MJ Boda (eds.), *Translating the New Testament: Text, Translation, Theology* (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 2009), 17.

⁴⁶⁰ Although the *Textus Receptus* shares certain features with later text-critical text editions (specifically the use of multiple source manuscripts where editorial choices are to be made with regard to textual variants), it is generally not regarded as text-critical since this presupposes a certain methodology that only emerged later with, for example, Westcott and Hort.

The marking ^(D) in table 2 for the *Codex Vaticanus* refers to the presence of a distigme (umlaut)⁴⁶¹ near 1 Cor. 16:2.⁴⁶² Wieland Willker⁴⁶³ describes this as follows:

In 1995 Philip Payne discovered the so called "umlauts" or double dots. These are two small horizontally aligned points like those above the German ä, ö, or ü. They are in the margin of the columns next to a line and are scattered all over the NT. Payne concluded and all scholars seem to agree with him, that these umlauts indicate lines where a textual variant was known to the person who wrote the umlauts.⁴⁶⁴

In 2006, Payne published an article called '*Using the umlauts of vaticanus to dig deeper*⁴⁶⁵ in which he addresses, among other things, the question of when the distigmai (umlauts) were placed. The ink of a distigme near 1 Cor. 16:2^a has also been examined as part of an investigation. As a result of this research, Payne and Canart state that 'the ink of the text-critical symbols in the *Codex Vaticanus*⁴⁶⁶ corresponds to the ink of the codex itself'.⁴⁶⁷ It follows that *Codex Vaticanus* can also be counted as a textual witness to (the early existence of) an alternative reading, most likely σαββάτων.

The writing by St. Basil the Great [ca. 329–379] could also be considered an additional textual witness from the fourth century. In *Morals 48.6*, Basil quotes the text from 1 Cor. 16:1-2 where he uses the plural form: κατὰ μίαν σαββάτων ἕκαστος ὑμῶν (...).⁴⁶⁸

⁴⁶¹ Philip Payne proposed in January 2009 to use 'distigme' instead of 'umlaut'. Philip Payne has published a lot of information about this subject on his personal website: <https://www.pbpayne.com>.

⁴⁶² The distigme related to 1 Cor. 16:2 is before the top line in the middle column: "... ΒΑΤΟΥΕΚΑΤΟCYMW".

⁴⁶³ Before his death, Willker worked at NMR Spektroskopie, Institut für Organische Chemie, at the University of Bremen. After his death, the family preserved his personal homepage and made it available at <https://www.willker.de/wie/>.

⁴⁶⁴ Wieland Willker, "Codex Vaticanus Graece 1209, B/03, The Umlauts", accessed 10 May 2021, <http://www.willker.de/wie/Vaticanus/umlauts.html>.

⁴⁶⁵ Gary S. Dykes, *Using the "Umlauts" of Codex Vaticanus to Dig Deeper* (sl: sn, 2006). http://www.biblical-data.org/BOX/BYZANTINE_UMLAUTS.pdf.

⁴⁶⁶ Vaticanus1 (δ 1 von Soden) refers to codex B.

⁴⁶⁷ Philip B. Payne and Paul Canart, The Originality of Text-Critical Symbols in *Codex Vaticanus, Novum Testamentum* 42 (2000), 105–113. <https://doi.org/10.1163/156853600506799>.

⁴⁶⁸ St. Basil the Great, "Morals 48.6" in *On Christian Ethics: Text*, Vol. 51, ed. J. Behr (Yonkers, NY: St. Vladimir's Seminary Press, 2014), 196.

APPENDIX 3: THE BIBLICAL FESTIVALS

This thesis extensively references details related to the cycle of the biblical spring feasts. Because these details and their interdependence are not generally known, and a good understanding of them is helpful for following the argument properly, this appendix provides a brief introduction.⁴⁶⁹

The biblical spring feasts function as a foundation and typological blueprint (antetype) for church spring feasts such as Good Friday, Easter, and Pentecost. The biblical spring feasts are the first part of the annual cycle of anniversaries given in Leviticus 23:1 and are described as מועדי יהוה, the appointed times of the LORD. Table 3 provides an overview:

Period	Memorial day(s)	Hebrew name	Constitutive texts
Spring	Passover	פֶּסַח	Lev. 23:5; Ex. 12:21-28; Deut. 16:1&2, 16:5-7
	Unleavened bread	מַצּוֹת	Lev. 23:6-8, Ex. 12:17-20, 13:5-7, Deut. 16:3&4&8
	Wave Sheaf Offering ⁴⁷⁰	עֹמֶר רֵאשִׁית	Lev. 23:10-15; Deut. 16:9
	(Omer Period)	סְפִירַת הָעוֹמֶר	Lev. 23:15; Deut. 16:9
	Festival of Weeks	שָׁבוּעוֹת	Lev. 23:16-22; Deut. 16:10&11
Autumn	Day of Trumpets ⁴⁷¹	יוֹם תְּרוּעָה	Lev. 23:24&25; Num. 29:1-6
	Great Day of Atonement	יוֹם כִּיפּוּר	Lev. 23:27-32; Num. 29:7-11
	Feast of Tabernacles	סֻכּוֹת	Lev. 23:34-36 ^a , Deut. 16:13-15, Num. 29:12-34
	The 'eighth day' ⁴⁷²	שְׁמִינִי עֶצְרַת	Lev. 23:36 ^b , Num. 29:35-38

Table 3: Overview of appointed times of the LORD

In this overview the Omer Period is bracketed because, strictly speaking, this is not an appointed time (מועד), but an instruction on how the date of the Wave Sheaf Offering and the Feast of Weeks are connected to each other. This is expressed in *practice* through the symbolic 'counting of the omer'⁴⁷³ as a *memoria* of the daily

⁴⁶⁹ On the subject discussed in this appendix, I am indebted to the insights gained during discussions with, among others, Drs. Jacob Keegstra (Stichting ICEJ-NL), Jaap Heringa (Stichting Moadim), Anton de Ruyter (Stichting Shoresh) and Drs. Bob van Dijk.

⁴⁷⁰ This day is known by several names: Wave Sheaf Day, Wave Sheaf Offering, 'Day of the First Fruits' (of the Barley Harvest) or First Fruits Feast. In this thesis, this day is called 'day of the sheaf of firstfruits' or in short 'sheaf of firstfruits' because it refers both to customs (the waving of the sheaf) and purpose (the principle of firstfruits as applied in 1 Cor. 15:20-23).

⁴⁷¹ More commonly known as the 'Jewish New Year' (ראש השנה, Rosh HaShanah).

⁴⁷² As the eighth day of the seven-day Feast of Tabernacles, it is often taken together with the preceding Feast of Tabernacles. This day is also known as 'Simchat Torah' (שמחת תורה) which can be translated as 'Rejoicing in the Torah'.

⁴⁷³ סְפִירַת הָעוֹמֶר.

portion of manna in the desert.⁴⁷⁴ Because of this connection, the Feast of Weeks can be seen as the completion of Passover.⁴⁷⁵ The Feast of Weeks is better known as Pentecost because it falls on the 50th day after the day of the Wave Sheaf Offering and is therefore called *πεντηκοστή* in the LXX and NT.

The table given earlier divides the appointed times into a spring and autumn cycle with the sacred calendar following the agricultural harvest cycle. The biblical calendar is therefore a combined lunar/sun calendar. A year normally lasts 354 days with 12 lunar months of 29 or 30 days.⁴⁷⁶ In order not to be out of step with agriculture, a 13th month is inserted before the month of Aviv if necessary.⁴⁷⁷ Because it is essential to be able to offer a worthy sacrifice to satisfy the entire nation on the day of the Sheaf of First Fruits,⁴⁷⁸ it is determined in the month of Adar whether an additional month (Adar Bet) should be inserted.⁴⁷⁹ After all, at the beginning of the month of Aviv, the barley ears must be 'aviv' (that is, 'green and almost ripe')⁴⁸⁰ so that the wave sheaf (a sheaf of barley) can be presented at exactly the right time.

The complete Biblical calendar has three rising or pilgrimage feasts.⁴⁸¹ Each of these is connected to bringing in a certain portion of the harvest:

Pesach/Unleavened bread: barley harvest.

Feast of Weeks: wheat harvest.

Feast of Tabernacles: the 'seven fruits of the land'.

Typologically, the autumn feasts stand for the final ingathering and completion (the 7 fruits symbolize the whole) of what was begun during the spring feasts with the ingathering of the firstfruits (symbolized by barley and wheat).

The diagram given below shows the relationship between the main Biblical spring festivals and the place of the Omer Period ('the Sabbaths') within them. To allow for such a rendering, choices about the date of Pesach and the interpretation of the "on the day after the Sabbath"⁴⁸² of Lev. 23:11 necessary. With every choice in this regard, counterarguments are possible, so that absolute certainty is

⁴⁷⁴ In rabbinic Judaism this is practically worked out with a daily prayer having, among other things, the 'sequential number' of the day.

⁴⁷⁵ This is expressed, for example, in the Mishna (Rosh Hashanah 16a) and Gemara (Pesachim 68b). The Feast of Weeks is called the 'Atseret' (closing gathering) (of Pesach).

⁴⁷⁶ Added note in comparison to the original thesis: A (biblical) month started at the new moon, which in ancient Israel was determined by visible sighting with the naked eye, hence the variance in the length of individual months.

⁴⁷⁷ The month of Aviv is referred to by the Babylonian name 'Nisan' in later writings (Neh. 2:1 and Est. 3:7) and in the present-day Jewish calendar.

⁴⁷⁸ Lev. 23:11.

⁴⁷⁹ Through years of observation, a pattern consisting of a cycle of 19 years (similar to the cycle of the Greek astronomer Meton) was noticed, on the basis of which the necessary intercalary months have long been inserted.

⁴⁸⁰ See Rashi's commentary on Ex. 23:15 in Chabad.org, "Shemot - Exodus - Chapter 23 (Parshah Mishpatim)", visited 10 January 2022, https://www.chabad.org/library/bible_cdo/aid/9884/showrashi/true.

⁴⁸¹ C.f. Deut. 16:16.

⁴⁸² מִן־הַיּוֹם הַשֶּׁבִּיעִי

impossible.⁴⁸³ While other choices have implications for practical implementation, they do not materially affect the concept of 'the Sabbaths' because both duration (49 days) and primary function (connecting Wave Sheaf Offering to the Feast of Weeks) are the same in each possible scheme.

The scheme used, here and in the rest of this thesis, will be based on the calendar system of the Sadducees⁴⁸⁴ and their way of determining (the day of the) Wave Sheaf Offering.⁴⁸⁵ This has been done for several reasons. First, by doing so the necessary condition for harmonization between LXX and the passion narratives is (broadly) fulfilled.⁴⁸⁶ Secondly, it can be used to explain the further historical course of church history. This particularly concerns the later importance of Sunday and the arguments surrounding the Quartodeciman controversy.⁴⁸⁷ The crucial point of the Quartodecimans was Jesus' crucifixion on the 14th of Nisan, falling on a variable day of the week, corresponding to the Passover according to the Sadducee calendar system. Her opponents emphasized the moment of Christ's resurrection and advocated Easter Sunday as the benchmark. In the Sadducee calendar system, the day of the Wave Sheaf Offering (\approx Easter Sunday) always falls on Yom Rishon (\approx Sunday).⁴⁸⁸ The proposed scheme thus simultaneously does justice to both historical positions on key points. The third argument is supportive and is related to the variable number of days between Pesach and Wave Sheaf Offering within this model. However, the historical realization of such a 'variable number of days' model has, with the passion narrative, a fixed number of days between Pesach (\approx Good Friday) and Wave Sheaf Offering (\approx Easter).⁴⁸⁹ It is my hypothesis that, due to a waning understanding of the structure of the Biblical festivals and increasing emphasis on historical elements surrounding the Passion, the Church's annual observance has shifted to a more simple model with a fixed number of days between (what is now called) Good Friday and Easter Sunday. Rabbinic Judaism, which emerged from Pharisaic Judaism after the destruction of the Second Temple, also uses a method of calculation with fixed dates. The day of the Wave Sheaf Offering then always falls on the 16th of Aviv and the Feast of Weeks on the 6th of Sivan.⁴⁹⁰ Being fixed

⁴⁸³ Dr. van Goudoever distinguishes four calculation methods. In Dr. J. van Goudoever, *Biblical Calendars*, second revised edition (Leiden: Brill, 1961), 12-13.

⁴⁸⁴ Likewise the present-day Karaites and the (historical) Bothusians according to Bab. Menah. 65A in: *The Babylonian Talmud: A Translation and Commentary*, Vol. 19, ed. Jacob Neusner (Peabody, MA: Hendrickson Publishers, 2011), 335.

⁴⁸⁵ The most well-known alternative, currently common within Rabbinic Judaism, follows the Pharisee method of calculation using fixed dates.

⁴⁸⁶ A common counterargument based on Josh. 5:11 assumed equality between מִחֲרַת הַשָּׁבֹת and מִחֲרַת הַפֶּסַח which, however, is unproven.

⁴⁸⁷ See e.g. Eusebius, "Hist. eccl. 5.23" in *Eusebius' Ecclesiastical History*, complete and unabridged, new updated edition, trans. C. F. Cruse (Peabody, MA: Hendrickson Publishers, 2014), 181.

⁴⁸⁸ According to E. Vogt, this is in accordance with the priestly calendar. Vogt, E., "Hat 'Šabbāt' im AT den Sinn von 'Woche'?" in *Biblica* 40 (1959), 1009.

⁴⁸⁹ Remarkably, a historical realization with Good Friday and Easter Sunday could be simultaneously compatible with both the Pharisaic and Sadducean views.

⁴⁹⁰ As the first day of a two-day celebration.

dates on this calendar, they both do not automatically fall on a Yom Rishon (≈ Sunday). If rabbinic Judaism and Christianity indeed developed antithetically, this contradictory position can be seen as supporting the chosen scheme.

It should also be noted that throughout history the dates of the Ecclesiastical holidays have become increasingly detached from their Biblical antetype, although they sometimes coincide. In this diagram, therefore, they have deliberately not been aligned below each other.

Biblical festivals (Lev. 23):

Diagram 1: Biblical and Ecclesiastical anniversaries

In this diagram, both Wave Sheaf Offering (≈ Easter Sunday) and the first day of the Feast of Weeks (≈ Pentecost) occur on Yom Rishon (≈ Sunday). According to CCC 1164, the 'People of God' had established festivals since the legislation of Moses. Indeed, these two Sundays were already set apart as antetype from Moses onward and the New Testament redemptive-historical events that took place on these days were typological fulfillments thereof.⁴⁹¹

The exact moment (day and hour) of Christ's resurrection has been left blank in this diagram because of textual ambiguities. Dionysius of Alexandria (200–265 CE) expressed this in his letter to Basilides as follows:

But in what you have written to me you have made out very clearly, and with an intelligent understanding of the Holy Scriptures, that no very exact account seems to be offered in them of the hour at which He rose. For the evangelists have given different

⁴⁹¹ For example, as indicated in Acts 2:1^a: Καὶ ἐν τῷ συμπληροῦσθαι τὴν ἡμέραν τῆς πεντηκοστῆς.

descriptions of the parties who came to the sepulcher one after another,⁴⁹² and all have declared that they found the Lord risen already. It was “in the end of the Sabbath,” as Matthew has said;⁴⁹³ it was “early, when it was yet dark,” as John writes;⁴⁹⁴ it was “very early in the morning,” as Luke puts it; and it was “very early in the morning, at the rising of the sun,” as Mark tells us. Thus no one has shown us clearly the exact time when He rose. It is admitted, however, that those who came to the sepulcher in the end of the Sabbath, as it began to dawn toward the first day of the week,⁴⁹⁵ found Him no longer lying in it.⁴⁹⁶

If this Yom Rishon were the day of the Resurrection, then Christ would have risen sometime between 'Saturday around sunset' and 'Sunday early morning'.⁴⁹⁷ However, uncertainty about the exact moment of the resurrection has no impact on what is stated in this thesis regarding Wave Sheaf Offering and the Omer Period. Christ's appearance before the Father took place on Wave Sheaf Offering, which includes Easter Sunday (until nightfall). In that span of time, Christ was exalted as also CCC 1166⁴⁹⁸ shows by quoting St. Jerome.⁴⁹⁹ Regardless of which schedule is followed, that is also when the Omer Period started and the counting of 'the Sabbaths' began.

⁴⁹² κατὰ καιροῦς ἐνηλλαγμένους (this and the following 3 footnotes are taken from *Fathers of the Third Century*).

⁴⁹³ Matt. 28:1.

⁴⁹⁴ John 20:1.

⁴⁹⁵ τῇ ἐπιφωσκούσῃ μιᾷ Σαββάτων.

⁴⁹⁶ Dionysius of Alexandria, “The Epistle to Bishop Basilides” in *Fathers of the Third Century: Gregory Thaumaturgus, Dionysius the Great, Julius Africanus, Anatolius and Minor Writers, Methodius, Arnobius*, Vol. 6, eds. A. Roberts, J. Donaldson & A.C. Coxe, trans. S. D. F. Salmond (Buffalo, NY: Christian Literature Company, 1886), 94.

⁴⁹⁷ If the '3 days and 3 nights' (Matt. 12:40) is literally understood as 72 hours, the resurrection would have taken place even at the end of the Sabbath (and shifts 'Good Friday' to a Wednesday).

⁴⁹⁸ *Catechism*, 267.

⁴⁹⁹ Quotation taken from St. Jerome, “Epistola XXII.IV” in *Patrologiæ course completus, series Latina, tomus XXX, tomus undecimus*, ed. J.-P. Migne (Parisina: J.-P. Migne, 1846), col. 212. <https://books.google.nl/books?id=j2hhs5X-aLwC&pg=PA211>.